

Appendix III.1.			
NESCent Year 3 Awards - December 1, 2006 - November 30, 2007			
Name	Institution	Project Name	Comments
<u>Postdoctoral Fellows</u>			
Brian O'Meara	Univ of California, Davis	Methods to examine trait evolution on trees: advancing the field	November 2007
Paula Spaeth	Stanford University	Competition and meso-evolutionary change in the mammalian fossil record	December 2007
<u>Third Year Postdoctoral Fellow Funding</u>			
Kirsten Fisher	NESCent	The phylogenomics of desiccation tolerance in the land plants	September 2007
David Kidd	NESCent	Phylogeographical information science: linking phylogenies and earth history	October 2007
Samantha Price	NESCent	Cetartiodactyl evolution: understanding the evolutionary transition from the terrestrial to the aquatic biome	November 2007
<u>Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
George Gilchrist	College of William & Mary	Evolution of Performance Curves in Seasonal Environments	9-mos, Sept08-May09
Malcolm Schug	UNC-Greensboro	The role of crossing-over and recombination in adaptive evolution	9-mos, Sept07-May08
<u>Catalysis Group</u>			
Daniel Hartline, David Colman, Petra Hoepcke Lenz, Mark Martindale, Elaine Seaver, Gunter Paul Wagner	Univ Hawaii, McGill Univ, Univ Hawaii, Univ Hawaii, Univ Hawaii, Yale Univ	Myelin, a new model for evolutionary innovation	September 2007
<u>Working Groups</u>			
Michael Schwartz, Fred Allendorf	USDA Forest Service, Univ of Montana	Genetic monitoring: Development of tools for conservation and management (w/ NCEAS)*	Joint w/NCEAS
Lauren Buckley, Michael Angilletta, Robert Holt, Joshua Tewksbury	Santa Fe Institute, Indiana St Univ, Univ Florida, Univ Washington	Mechanistic distribution models: energetics, fitness, and population dynamics	Joint w/NCEAS - NCEAS 11/2007; NESCent 3/2008
Samantha Forde, Ivana Gudelj	Univ of California, Santa Cruz; Univ of Bath, UK	Mathematical models, microbes & evolutionary diversification*	March 2008
Diddahal Govindaraju, Andrew Clark, Trudy Mackay, Stephen Stearns	Boston Univ, Cornell Univ, North Carolina St Univ, Yale Univ	Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations*	March/April 2008
Kenneth Kozak, Catherine Graham, Carsten Rahbek	Univ of Minnesota, Stony Brook Univ, Univ of Copenhagen	Montane diversity in space and time*	January 2008
David Lahti & Susan A. Foster	Univ of Massachusetts, Clark Univ	Relaxed selection and trait loss in evolution	August 2007
Charles Nunn & Brian Hare	UC Berkeley, Duke Univ	How does cognition evolve?	January 2008

Appendix III.2.

**Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists
at the Center in Year 3**

Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>Postdoctoral Fellows</u>			
Burleigh, Gordon	Univ of California - Davis	A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants	Nov 2006
Fisher, Kirsten	Univ of California - Berkeley	The Phylogenomics of Desiccation Tolerance in the Land Plants	Sept 2005
Ganapathy, Ganeshkumar	Univ of Texas - Austin	New DCM Methods for ML, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography	Dec 2006
Granek, Joshua	Johns Hopkins Univ	Comparative Genomic Studies of the Sequences Responsible for the Regulation of Gene Expression	Aug 2005 - July 2007
Hazkani-Covo, Einat	Tel-Aviv University	Numt Variation in Metazoan Genomes: Gain, Loss, Duplication and Possible Function	March 2006
Hereford, Joe	Floria St Univ, Tallahassee	Adaptive Divergence Between Natural Populations	Sept 2005 - Dec 2006
Hoeksema, Jason	Univ of California - Santa Cruz	What is the Relative Importance of Biotic vs. Abiotic Local Adaptation?	July 2006 - July 2007
Hopkins, Samantha	Univ of California - Berkeley	The Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality: Causes and Consequences	Aug 2006 - Aug 2007
Kidd, David	Univ of St. Andrews, UK	Phylogeographical Information Science: Linking Phylogenies and Earth History	Oct 2005
McCall, Lauren W.	Univ Cambridge	Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution	Jan 2007
O'Meara, Brian	Univ of California, Davis	Methods to Examine Trait Evolution in Trees: Advancing the Field	Nov 2007
Price, Samantha	Univ of Virginia	Cetartiodactyl Evolution: Understanding the Evolutionary Transition from the Terrestrial to the Aquatic Biome	Nov 2005
Sidlauskas, Brian	Univ Chicago	Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas	Sept 2006
Zanne, Amy	Masaryk Univ, Brno, Czech Rep	Hydraulic Efficiency and Safety: Do Tradeoffs have an Evolutionary Basis in the Rosids?	Aug 2006 w/NSF postdoc fellowship; NESCent postdoc begins May 2007.
Zwickl, Derrick	Univ of Texas, Austin	Implementation of a Wide Range of Codon and Amino Acid Models in Bayesian Phylogenetic Software	Jan 2006
<u>Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Eernisse, Douglas	Calif St Univ - Fullerton	Chiton Phylogeny and Comparative Phylogeography	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Fail, Jr., Joseph	Johnson C. Smith Univ	Designing and Teaching an Evolution Curriculum for Elementary Students	12-mos, Sept 2006 - Aug 2007
Otto, Sarah	Univ of British Columbia	A Community Approach to Evolutionary Theory	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Schug, Malcolm	Univ of North Carolina at Greensboro	The Role of Crossing-over and Recombination in Adaptive Evolution	9-mos, Sept 2007 - May 2008
Whitlock, Michael	Univ of British Columbia	Evolution in a Spatial Context: A Synthesis of Theory and Review	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007

Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center in Year 3			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>Senior Research Scientist</u>			
Swofford, David	Joint Duke position w/ Inst for Genome Sci & Policy	PAUP, Phylogenetics, Computational Biology	Oct 2007
Local Scientists at the Center in Year 3			
<u>Visiting Scholars without NESCent Funding</u>			
Jones, Clara B.	Fayetteville State Univ	Solving the Alouatta Paradox: From Polygyny to Polygynandry	April 2006-March 2008
Roth, V. Louise	Duke Univ	Squirrels as Models in Macroevolution; Scaling	Jan-Dec 2007
<u>Triangle Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Pfennig, David	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	Phenotypic Plasticity and the Origins of Diversity	Sept-Dec 2007
Rausher, Mark	Duke Univ	Evolutionary Genetics and Molecular Evolution	Jan-May 2007
Servedio, Maria	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	Analysis of Factors that Determine the Occurrence of Speciation and Reinforcement	Sept-Dec 2006
Willis, John	Duke Univ	Evolutionary Genomics and Bioinformatics of Mimulus, a Developing Model System for Studies of Plant Adaptation and Speciation	Sept-Dec 2006
<u>At-Large Members of the Operations Committee</u>			
Clarke, Julia	North Carolina St Univ	N/A	Sept 2007-Dec 2007
Gensel, Patricia	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	N/A	Jan 2006-Dec 2007
Wiegmann, Brian	North Carolina St Univ	N/A	Jan 2006-Aug 2007
Wray, Greg	Duke Univ	N/A	July 2006-Dec 2007

Appendix III.3.			
NESCent Seminar Series			
Year 3			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Dec-1-2006	Michael Whitlock	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, University of British Columbia, Canada	Evolution in a Spatial Context
Dec-08-2006	Dr. Joseph Fail, Jr.	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Johnson C. Smith Univ	The Importance of Early Education in Evolution, its Current State in North Carolina, and a Suggested Approach for Teaching Evolution to Elementary Students
Dec-12-2006	Dr. Charles Baer	Department of Zoology University of Florida	Standing and Mutational Variation for Fitness in <i>Caenorhabditis</i>
Dec-15-2006	Dr. Samantha Hopkins	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Down the Rabbit Hole: Convergence and Dead-End Adaptation in the Evolution of Fossoriality
Jan-19-2007	Dr. Patricia Gensel	NESCent Operations Committee, UNC-Chapel Hill	Tales From Deep Time-Early Land Plant Evolution
Jan-26-2007	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Brian Rybarczyk	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program & Director of Educational Support Programs Graduate School, UNC-Chapel Hill	Effective Teaching via Video Teleconference Including a Demo Between NESCent and UNC-Chapel Hill
Feb-02-2007	Dr. Clara B. Jones	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Fayetteville State Univ	Environmental Noise, Demographic Signals and the Conditions Favoring Male Sociality
Feb-16-2007	Dr. Jory Weintraub	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Applying and Interviewing for Faculty Jobs in Evolutionary Biology (Part 2) - A Roundtable Discussion with NESCent Sabbatical Scholars and Directors
Feb-23-2007	Dr. Ganesh Ganapathy	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Pattern Identification in Biogeography
Mar-02-2007	Dr. Sally Otto	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ of British Columbia, Canada	Open Discussion on: Identifying and Applying for Faculty Positions in Evolutionary Biology: A Roundtable Discussion with NESCent Directors and Sabbatical Scholars
Mar-09-2007	Dr. Lisa Horth	Assistant Professor of Biological Sciences, Old Dominion University	The Synthesis of Ecology, Evolution and Genetics Best Explains the Persistence of Very Rare Melanic Mosquitofish in Nature
Mar-16-2007	Dr. Lauren McCall	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	What is Biological About Cultural Evolution?
Mar-22-2007	Dr. David Ackerly	Department of Integrative Biology, University of California Berkeley	Climate and Plants in California: Past, Present and Future
Mar-23-2007	Dr. Mark Rausher	NESCent Triangle Sabbatical Scholar, Duke Univ	Genetics of Flower Color Evolution

NESCent Seminar Series			
Year 3			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Mar-30-2007	Dr. Robert Peet	Professor and Chair Curriculum in Ecology, UNC-Chapel Hill	Intellectual Property Curriculum in Ecology, UNC-Chapel Hill
Apr-27-2007	Dr. Steve Nowicki	Professor in the Depts. of Biology, Psychology and Neurobiology and Dean of Natural Sciences, Duke University	Negotiating Your First Faculty Position: A Roundtable Discussion with Dr. Steve Nowicki
May-11-2007	Dr. Todd Vision	NESCent Associate Director for Informatics UNC-Chapel Hill	Known Unknown: How Well Can we Predict Gene Content and Order in Unsequenced Genomes?
May-18-2007	Dr. Erich Jarvis	Associate Professor, Dept. of Neurobiology, Duke Univ	Evolution of Brain Pathways for Vocal Learning
May-25-2007	Dr. Shelah Morita	NESCent Scientist Dept. of Entomology, NC State Univ	Independent Evolution of Both Long and Short Proboscis Morphology in the Philoliche Aethiopica Species Complex (Diptera: Tabanidae)
Jun-01-2007	Dr. Samantha Price	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	A Roundtable Discussion on Manuscript Submission: Where? Why? When?
Jun-15-2007	Dr. Einat Hazkani-Covo	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	What Can evolution Teach Us About Double Strand Break Repair
Jun-22-2007	Dr. V. Louise Roth	NESCent Triangle Fellow and Associate Professor, Duke Univ	Scaling Tales
Jun 29-2007	Dr. Donna Bailey	Director, TA Development Program, UNC Center for Teaching and Learning, UNC-Chapel Hill	Research and Mentoring: Two Sides of the Same Coin
Jul-6-2007	Dr. Greg Gibson	NESCent Associate Director of Education and Outreach, NC State Univ	The Human Transition Project
Jul-20-2007	Dr. Jason Hoeksema	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Progress in Our Understanding of Local Adaptation Between Interacting Species
Sep-07-2007	Dr. Kirsten Fisher	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Everything You Ever Wanted to Know About Moss, But Were Afraid to Ask
Sep-14-2007	Dr. Derrick Zwickl	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	What I Did During My Summer Vacation: Updates on Several Ongoing Projects
Sep-20-2007	Dr. Günter Wagner	Alison Richard Professor & Chair of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Yale Univ	Molecular Evolution of Novel Characters: The Origin of Novel Gene Regulatory Networks
Sep-28-2007	Karl Bates	Manager of Research Communications, Duke Univ	Why and How to Communicate About Your Science
Oct-05-2007	Dr. Brian O'Meara	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Using the Tree of Life: Honey-pot Ants, Character Evolution and Species Delimitation

NESCent Seminar Series			
Year 3			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Oct-12-2007	Dr. Malcolm Schug	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, UNC-Greensboro	Mate Discrimination and Incipient Speciation Among Populations for Fruitflies from Asia and the South Pacific
Oct-19-2007	Dr. Gordon Burleigh	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	TBA
Oct-26-2007	Dr. David Pfenning	NESCent Triangle Sabbatical Scholar, UNC-Chapel Hill	Polyphenism and the Origins of Diversity
Nov-02-2007	Dr. David Kidd	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	TBA
Nov-09-2007	Dr. Marcy Uyenoyama	Professor of Biology, Duke Univ	TBA
Nov-16-2007	Dr. Kathleen Smith	NESCent Director, Duke Univ	TBA
Nov-30-2007	Dr. Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	TBA

Appendix III.4.**Current Positions of Postdoctoral Fellows Completing NESCent Funding**

Name	Appointment	Current Employment	Starting Date
Granek, Joshua	Postdoctoral Research Associate	Department of Biology, Duke University	August 1, 2007
Hereford, Joe	Postdoctoral Fellow	Department of Biology, University of Maryland, College Park	January 1, 2007
Hoeksema, Jason	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Mississippi	August 1, 2007
Hopkins, Samantha	Assistant Professor	Clark Honors College, University of Oregon	September 1, 2007
Zanne, Amy	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Missouri, St Louis	August 1, 2008

Appendix III.5.				
NESCent Meetings				
Year 3, December 1, 2006 - November 30, 2007				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Attendees	Type
December 1 - 5, 2006	Kalisz, Susan Johnston, Mark	Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants	10	Work Group
December 11 - 15, 2006	Lapp, Hilmar	First NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon	20	Informatics
December 13 - 14, 2006	Jungck, John Weosstein, Anton E.	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in AcTION	12	Education Work Group
December 17 - 19, 2006	Uyenoyama, Marcy Tokuta, Alade Nielsen, Rasmus	Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression	15	Triangle Work Group
January 4 - 6, 2007	Carter, Pat	Evolution of Function-Valued Traits	35	Hosted
January 12 - 14, 2007	Macaluso, Andrea	Evolutionary Editorial Board Meeting	12	Hosted
January 15 - 16, 2007	NSF	National Science Foundation Site Visit	10	Site Visit
February 1 -2, 2007	Kingsolver, Joel	Scientific Advisory Board	15	Advisory
February 2 - 5, 2007	Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer Kowalewski, Michael	Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: macroevolution and macroecology	12	Work Group
March 12 - 15, 2007	Donoghue, Michael Manos, Paul	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere	15	Work Group
March 15 - 17, 2007	Bergman, Casey Keitman, Martin Dermitzakis, Manolis	Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution.	12	Work Group
March 17, 2007	Simon, Chris	Society for Systematic Biologists Executive Board	10	Hosted
March 19 - 20, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood Density Meeting, Group 1 (27A)	8	Co-Sponsored

Appendix III.5.				
NESCent Meetings				
Year 3, December 1, 2006 - November 30, 2007				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Attendees	Type
March 21 - 22, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood Density Meeting, Group 2 (27B)	8	Co-Sponsored
March 23 - 24, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood Density Meeting, Group 3 (27C)	8	Co-Sponsored
April 1 - 3, 2007	Kocher, Tom	Genomic Approaches to the Study of Adaptive Radiation	30	Catalysis
April 4 - 7, 2007	Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	12	Work Group
April 14, 2007	Clarke, Julia Nagalingum, Nathalie Wiegmann, Brian	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology.	26	Triangle Work Group
April 19 - 20, 2007	Schindel, David	AToL/CBOL Meeting	30	Hosted
April 21 - 24, 2007	Cracraft, Joel Siddall, Mark	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography	14	Work Group
April 24 - 27, 2007	Peet, Bob	Toward an international exchange standard for vegetation and biodiversity co-occurrence data	10	Hosted
April 26, 2007	Fail, Joseph	Rashkis Elementary School of Chapel Hill: 5th Grade Class	28	Education
May 2 - 5, 2007	Hughes, Kim Breden, Felix Weigel, Detlef	Developing New Model Systems for Evolutionary Genomics Using Poeciliid Fishes	30	Catalysis
May 16 - 17, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar Vision, Todd	Data preservation, sharing, and discovery: Small science in the digital era	20	Informatics
May 21 - 23, 2007	Stoltzfus, Arlin Vos, Rutger	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis	14	Work Group

Appendix III.5.				
NESCent Meetings				
Year 3, December 1, 2006 - November 30, 2007				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Attendees	Type
May 24 - 27, 2007	Govindaraju, Raju Byers, Peter Stearns, Stephen	Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations: Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications	30	Catalysis
May 30 - 31, 2007	Duke, Cliff	Ecological Society of America: Obstacles to Data Sharing Workshop	40	Hosted
June 4 - 6, 2007	Plotnick, Roy	Origins and Evolution of Chemoreception	30	Catalysis
June 9-12, 2006	Jungck, John Weosstein, Anton E.	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in AcTION	12	Education Work Group
June 11-13, 2007	Leebens-Mack, Jim Brenner, Eric	The Plant EvoGenetics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics	17	Work Group
June 21, 2007	Weintraub, Jory Jenkins, Kristin	Careers in Evolution and Biology	17	Education Workshop
July 9-13, 2007	Fail, Joseph	NESCent Teacher Education Program	16	Education Course
July 9 - 19, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar Piel, William	Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course	15	Informatics Course
August 9 - 12, 2007	Alberts, Susan Strier, Karen Wright, Patricia	Primate Life Histories	12	Work Group
August 10-12, 2007	Lahti, David	Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution	13	Work Group
August 16 - 17, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar	Google Summer of Code Presentations Meeting	20	Informatics Course
August 23 - 24, 2008	Smith, Kathleen	Senior Advisory Board	10	Advisory
September 10 - 12, 2007	Tannen, Val	Processing PhyloData (pPOD): Core Database Technologies to Enable the Integration of AToL Information	20	Hosted

Appendix III.5.				
NESCent Meetings				
Year 3, December 1, 2006 - November 30, 2007				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Attendees	Type
September 17 - 18, 2007	Mabee, Paula Vision, Todd	PhenoMaP Needs Analysis Workshop	18	Collaborative Activity
September 17 - 19, 2007	Hartline, Daniel	Myelin, A New Model for Evolutionary Innovation	30	Catalysis
September 20 - 23, 2007	Kalisz, Susan Johnston, Mark	Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants	10	Work Group
September 21 - 24, 2007	Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer Kowalewski, Michael	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology	10	Work Group
October 4 - 7, 2007	Willis, John	Mimulus Evolution, Ecology and Genetics	25	Hosted
October 18 - 20, 2007	Donovan, Sam	EOG TREE	10	Education Work Group
October 18 - 20, 2007	Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	12	Work Group
October 25 - 27, 2007	Uno, Gordon Scotchmoor, Judy	Evolution Across the Curriculum	10	Education Work Group
November 29 - 30, 2007	Cracraft, Joel Siddall, Mark	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography	14	Work Group

Appendix III.6.

Participant Lists – NESCent Sponsored Meetings

December 1, 2006 – November 30, 2007

Catalysis Meetings

April 1 – 3, 2007

Genomic Approaches to the Study of Adaptive Radiation

Coordinator: Tom Kocher

Participants:

Craig Albertson
Etienne Bezault
Karen Carleton
Cristian Castillo-Davis
Hans Cheng
Pat Danley
Art Delcher
Gareth Fraser
Greg Gibson
Jody Hey
Hans Hofmann
Darrin Hulse
Tom Kocher
Irv Kornfield
Elliott Margulies
Rasmus Nielsen
Magnus Nordborg
Nori Okada
Susan Renn
Reade Roberts
Arindam Roy Choudhury
Ole Seehausen
Todd Strelman
George Turner

Syracuse University
University of Bern
University of Maryland
University of Maryland
ARS, Michigan State
University of Maryland
University of Maryland
University of Maryland
Georgia Institute of Technology
North Carolina State University
Rutgers University
University of Texas – Austin
Georgia Institute of Technology
University of Maryland
University of Maine
NHGRI
Cornell University
University of Southern California
Tokyo Institute of Technology
Reed College
University of New Hampshire
Harvard University
University of Bern, Switzerland
Georgia Institute of Technology
University of Hull, UK

May 2 – 5, 2007

Developing New Model Systems for Evolutionary Genomics Using Poeciliid Fishes

Coordinators: Kim Hughes

Felix Breden

Detlef Weigel

Participants:

Erik Baatrup
 Alexandra Basolo
 Felix Breden
 Rob Brooks
 Kerry Deere
 Christine Dreyer
 Phil Hedrick
 Hans Hofmann
 Anne Houde
 Kimberly Hughes
 Jerry Johnson
 David Kingsley
 Mark Kirkpatrick
 Anne Magurran
 David Parichy
 David Reznick
 Helen Rodd
 Manfred Scharl
 Suzanne Schories
 Joe Travis
 Ronald Walter
 Detlef Weigel

University of Aarhus
 University of Nebraska
 Simon Fraser University
 The University of New South Wales
 University of California – Los Angeles
 Max-Planck-Institut für Entwicklungsbiologie
 Arizona State University
 The University of Texas – Austin
 Lake Forest College
 University of Illinois – Urbana-Champaign
 Brigham Young University
 HHMI and Stanford University
 University of Texas – Austin
 University of St. Andrews
 University of Washington
 University of California – Riverside
 University of Toronto
 Universität Würzburg
 Universität Würzburg
 Florida State University
 Texas State University
 Max-Planck-Institut für Entwicklungsbiologie

May 24 – 27, 2007

**Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations:
 Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications**

Coordinators: Raju Govindaraju

Peter Byers

Stephen Stearns

Participants:

Peter Byers
 Lon Cardon
 Andrew Clark
 Peter Ellison
 James Evans
 Caleb Finch
 Raju Govindaraju
 Adrian Hill
 Eddie Holmes
 Magdalena Hurtado
 David Jones
 Lynn Jorde
 Mary-Claire King
 Jacob Koella
 Charles Lee

University of Washington
 University of Washington
 Cornell University
 Harvard University
 University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
 University of Southern California
 Boston University
 Oxford University
 Pennsylvania State University
 University of New Mexico
 Massachusetts Institute of Technology
 University of Utah
 University of Washington
 Imperial College
 Harvard University

Sandra Lee
Bruce Levin
Trudy Mackay
Cynthia Morton
Joanna Mountain
Randolph Nesse
Stephen Stearns
Shamil Sunyaev
Ezra Susser
David Valle
Greg Wray
Sebastian Zoellner

Stanford University
Emory University
North Carolina State University
Harvard Medical School
Stanford Medical School
University of Michigan
Yale University
Harvard University
Columbia University
Johns Hopkins University
Duke University
University of Michigan

June 4 – 6, 2007

**Origins and Evolution of Chemoreception
Coordinator: Roy Plotnick**

Participants:

Jelle Atema
Jennifer Basil
John Crimaldi
Sasha Dall
Charles Derby
Heather Eisthen
Douglas Erwin
Frank Grasso
Michael Hadfield
John Hildebrand
David Jacobs
Mimi Koehl
Karen Koy
Conrad Labandeira
Robert Lane
Sara Lindsay
Chris Lowe
Hiroaki Matsunami
Paul Moore
Roy Plotnick
Hugh Robertson
Steve Rowland
Kurt Schwenk
Peter Sorensen
Jackson Sparks
Nicholas Strausfeld
Judith Van Houten
Richard Vogt
Marc Weissberg

Boston University
Brooklyn College
University of Colorado
University of Exeter
Georgia State University
Michigan State University
National Museum of Natural History
Brooklyn College
University of Hawaii
University of Arizona
University of California – Los Angeles
University of California – Berkeley
University of Illinois – Chicago
Smithsonian Institution
Wesleyan University
University of Maine
University of Chicago
Duke University
Bowling Green State University
University of Illinois – Chicago
University of Illinois – Urbana-Champaign
University of Nevada – Las Vegas
University of Connecticut
University of Minnesota
University of South Carolina
University of Arizona
University of Vermont
University of South Carolina
Georgia Institute of Technology

Donald Wilson
Richard Zimmer

University of Oklahoma
University of California – Los Angeles

September 17 – 19, 2007

Myelin: A New Model for Evolutionary Innovation
Coordinator: Daniel Hartline

Participants:

Manzoor Bhat
Ray Bauer
Ed Buskey
Ann Castelfranco
Andy Christie
Dave Colman
Robert Gould
Dan Hartline
Rob Jennings
David King
Petra Lenz
Mark Martindale
David McClellan
Robert Miller
Todd Oakley
Betty Roots
Elaine Seaver
Monica Vianna
Gunter Wagner
Hauke Wagner
Caroline Wilson

University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of Louisiana – Lafayette
University of Texas – Austin
University of Hawaii
University of Washington
McGill University
University of Illinois – Chicago
University of Hawaii
University of Connecticut – Avery Point
University of Southern Illinois
University of Hawaii
University of Hawaii
Brigham Young University
Case Western Reserve University
University of California – Santa Barbara
University of Toronto
University of Hawaii
Pontifical University Catholic – Rio Grande Do Sul
Yale University
Max Planck Institute – Goettingen
University of Hawaii

Working Groups

Science Working Groups

December 1 – 5, 2006

Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants

Coordinators: Susan Kalisz
Mark Johnston

Participants:

Pierre-Oliver Cheptou
Christopher Eckert
Elizabeth Elle
Monica Gerber
Carol Goodwillie
Mark Johnston
Susan Kalisz

CNRS
Queens University
Simon Fraser University
Cornell University
East Carolina University
Dalhousie University
University of Pittsburgh

John Kelley
David Moeller
Emmanuelle Porcher
Rick Ree
Risa Sargent
Marcy Uyenoyama
Mario Vallejo-Marin
Don Waller
Alice Winn

University of Kansas
University of Minnesota
University of California, San Diego
The Field Museum
University of British Columbia
Duke University
University of Toronto
University of Wisconsin
Florida State University

February 2 – 5, 2007

**Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space:
macroevolution and macroecology**

**Coordinators: Jonathan Payne
Jennifer Stempien
Michael Kowalweski**

Participants:

Alison Boyer
James Brown
Seth Finnegan
Michal Kowalweski
Richard Krause
Kathleen Lyons
Craig McClain
Daniel McShea
Philip Novack-Gottshall
Jonathan Payne
Felisa Smith
Jennifer Stempien
Steve Wang

University of New Mexico
University of New Mexico
Stanford University
Virginia Polytechnic Institute
Virginia Polytechnic Institute
NCEAS
Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute
Duke University
University of West Georgia
Stanford University
University of New Mexico
University of Colorado
Swarthmore College

March 12 – 15, 2007

Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere

**Coordinators: Michael Donoghue
Paul Manos**

Participants:

Michael Donoghue
Peter Fritsch
David Kidd
Jianhua Li
Steven Manchester
Paul Manos
Richard Milne
Brian Moore
Ren Redelings
Richard Ree

Yale University
California Academy of Sciences
NESCent
Harvard University
Florida Museum of Natural History
Duke University
University of Edinburgh
Yale University
North Carolina State University
Field Museum of Natural History

Susanne Renner
Bob Ricklefs
Stephen Smith
Jeff Thorne
Jun Wen
Jenny Xiang

University of Munich
University of Missouri – St. Louis
Yale University
North Carolina State University
Smithsonian Institute
North Carolina State University

March 15 – 17, 2007

Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution

**Coordinators: Casey Bergman
Martin Keitman
Manolis Dermitzakis**

Participants:

Casey Bergman
Manolis Dermitzakis
Marty Kreitman
Michael Eisen
Michael Lässig
Alan Moses
Adam Siepel
Pilar Fancino
Saurabh Sinha
Wyeth Wasserman
Eric Xing

University of Manchester
Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute
University of Chicago
University of California – Berkeley
Universität zu Köln
Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute
Cornell University
Joint Genome Institute
University of Illinois
University of British Columbia
Carnegie Mellon University

April 4 – 7, 2007

Modeling Variation in Gene Networks

**Coordinators: Paul Magwene
David Houle**

Participants:

Ralph Haygood
David Houle
Kerry Kim
Hao Li
Paul Magwene
Jason Mezey
Steve Proulx
Matt Rockman
Mark Siegal
Joshua Socolar
Patricia Wittkopp

Duke University
Florida State University
University of Washington
University of California – San Francisco
Duke University
Cornell University
Iowa State University
Princeton University
New York University
Duke University
University of Michigan

April 21 – 24, 2007

**Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for
Historical Biogeography**

Coordinators: Joel Cracraft

Mark Siddall

Participants:

Rachel Collin
Joel Cracraft
Michael Donoghue
Ganesh Ganapathy
Luay Nakhleh
Rod Page
Richard Ree
Mike Sanderson
Isabel Sanmartin
Mark Siddall
Stephen Smith
Tandy Warnow

Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
American Museum of Natural History
Yale University
NESCent
Rice University
University of Glasgow
Field Museum of Natural History
University of Arizona
Uppsala University
American Museum of Natural History
Yale University
University of Texas – Austin

May 21 – 23, 2007

**Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting
Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis**

Coordinators: Arlin Stoltzfus

Rutger Vos

Participants:

Gopal Gupta
Mark Holder
Sergei Kosakovsky Pond
Sudhir Kumar
Aaron Mackey
Enrico Pontelli
Weigang Qiu
Arlin Stoltzfus
David L. Swofford
Rutger Vos
Xuhua Xia
Christian Zmasek

University of Texas – Dallas
Florida State University
University of California – San Diego
Arizona State University
GlaxoSmithKline
New Mexico State University
Hunter College
National Institute of Standards and Technology
Florida State University
University of British Columbia
University of Ottawa
Burnham Institute for Medical Research

June 10 – 13, 2007

**The Plant Evolutionary Genomics Working Group:
Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics**

Coordinators: Jim Leebens-Mack

Eric Brenner

Participants:

Eric Brenner
Steve Cannon
Rob deSalle

New York Botanic Gardens
Iowa State University
American Museum of Natural History

Stefanie Hartmann
Jim Leebens-Mack
David Liberles
Andy Paterson
Bill Piel
Mike Sanderson
Shin-Han Shiu
Dennis Stevenson
Val Tannen
Todd Vision
Kerr Wall
Tandy Warnow

University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of Georgia
University of Wyoming
University of Georgia
Yale University
University of Arizona
Michigan State University
New York Botanic Gardens
University of Pennsylvania
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
Pennsylvania State University
University of Texas

August 9 – 12, 2007

Primate Life Histories

Coordinators: Susan Alberts

Karen Strier

Patricia Wright

Participants:

John Addicott
Susan Alberts
Jeanne Altmann
Diane Brockman
Anne Bronikowski
Marina Cords
Linda Fedigan
Bill Morris
Anne Pusey
Tara Stoinski
Karen Strier
Pat Wright
Jun Yang

University of Calgary
Duke University
Princeton University
University of North Carolina – Charlotte
Iowa State University
Columbia University
University of Calgary
Duke University
University of Minnesota
Zoo Atlanta and Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund
University of Wisconsin
Stony Brook University
Duke University

August 10 – 12, 2007

Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution

Coordinator: David Lahti

Participants:

Daniel Blumstein
Christina Burch
Richard Cross
Troy Day
Kathleen Donohue
Susan Foster
Norman Johnson
David Lahti

University of California – Los Angeles
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of California – Davis
Queens University
Harvard University
Clark University
University of Massachusetts
University of Massachusetts

September 20 – 23, 2007

Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants

**Coordinators: Susan Kalisz
Mark Johnston**

Participants:

Pierre-Oliver Cheptou
Christopher Eckert
Elizabeth Elle
Monica Gerber
Carol Goodwillie
Mark Johnston
Susan Kalisz
John Kelley
David Moeller
Emmanuelle Porcher
Rick Ree
Risa Sargent
Marcy Uyenoyama
Mario Vallejo-Marin
Alice Winn

CNRS
Queens University
Simon Fraser University
Cornell University
East Carolina University
Dalhousie University
University of Pittsburgh
University of Kansas
University of Minnesota
University of California, San Diego
The Field Museum
University of British Columbia
Duke University
University of Toronto
Florida State University

September 21 – 24, 2007

Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: macroevolution and macroecology

**Coordinators: Jonathan Payne
Jennifer Stempien
Michael Kowalweski**

Participants:

John Alroy
Alison Boyer
James Brown
Morgan Ernest
Seth Finnegan
David Jablonski
Michal Kowalweski
Richard Krause
Kathleen Lyons
Craig McClain
Daniel McShea
Philip Novack-Gottshall
Jonathan Payne
Felisa Smith
Jennifer Stempien
Steve Wang

NCEAS
University of New Mexico
University of New Mexico
University of Southern Utah
Stanford University
University of Chicago
Virginia Polytechnic Institute
Virginia Polytechnic Institute
NCEAS
Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute
Duke University
University of West Georgia
Stanford University
University of New Mexico
University of Colorado
Swarthmore College

October 18 – 20, 2007

Modeling Variation in Gene Networks

**Coordinators: Paul Magwene
David Houle**

Participants:

Duccio Cavalieri
Thomans Hansen
Ralph Haygood
David Houle
Kerry Kim
Hao Li
Paul Magwene
Jason Mezey
Jason Moore
Patrick Phillips
Steve Proulx
Matt Rockman
Mark Siegal
Joshua Socolar
Patricia Wittkopp

University of Florence
University of Oslo
Duke University
Florida State University
University of Washington
University of California – San Francisco
Duke University
Cornell University
Dartmouth College
University of Oregon
Iowa State University
Princeton University
New York University
Duke University
University of Michigan

November 29 – 30, 2007

**Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for
Historical Biogeography**

**Coordinators: Joel Cracraft
Mark Siddall**

Participants:

Rachel Collin
Joel Cracraft
Michael Donoghue
Ganesh Ganapathy
Luay Nakhleh
Rod Page
Richard Ree
Mike Sanderson
Isabel Sanmartin
Mark Siddall
Stephen Smith
Tandy Warnow

Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
American Museum of Natural History
Yale University
NESCent
Rice University
University of Glasgow
Field Museum of Natural History
University of Arizona
Uppsala University
American Museum of Natural History
Yale University
University of Texas – Austin

Education and Outreach Working Groups

December 13 – 14, 2006

**Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium:
Evolution in AcTION**

Coordinators: John Jungck

Anton E. Weosstein

Participants:

Sam Donovan
David Hillis
John Jungck
Stacey Kiser
Cindy Passmore
Katja Schultz
Judy Scotchmoor
Martha Wayne

University of Pittsburgh
University of Texas – Austin
BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium
Lane Community College
University of California – Davis
Tree of Life
University of California – Berkeley
University of Florida

June 9-12, 2007

**Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium:
Evolution in AcTION**

Coordinators: John Jungck

Anton E. Weosstein

Participants:

Bruno Borsari
Sam Donovan
Kristin Jenkins
John Jungck
Stacey Kiser
Claudia Neuhauser
Katja Schultz
Jennifer Stempien
Marta Wayne
Jory Weintraub
Tony Weisstein

Winona State University
University of Pittsburgh
NESCent
BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium
Lane Community College
University of Minnesota
Tree of Life
University of Colorado
University of Florida
NESCent
Truman State University

October 18 – 20, 2007

EOG TREE

Coordinator: Sam Donovan

Participants:

James J. Smith
Dan Gallagher
Stacey Kiser
Charles Bell
Kefyn Catley
Paul Beardsley

Michigan State University
Bellevue School District
Lane Community College
University of New Orleans
Western Carolina University
Biological Sciences Curriculum Study

J. Chris Pires
Sam Donovan
Jory Weintraub
Kristin Jenkins

University of Missouri – Columbia
University of Pittsburgh
NESCent
NESCent

October 25 – 27, 2007

Evolution Across the Curriculum
Coordinators: Judy Scotchmoor
Gordon Uno

Participants:

Paul Beardsley
Adam Fagen
Kristin Jenkins
Jay Labov
Judy Scotchmoor
Gordon Uno
Jory Weintraub

Biological Science Curriculum Study
The National Academies
NESCent
The National Academies
University of California – Berkeley
University of Oklahoma
NESCent

Informatics

December 11 – 15, 2006

First NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon
Coordinator: Hilmar Lapp

Participants:

Sendu Bala
Jim Balhoff
Amy Bouck
Jeff Chang
Naohisa Goto
Mark Holder
Richard Holland
Alisha Holloway
Toshiaki Katayama
Hilmar Lapp
Paul Lewis
Aaron Mackey
Spencer Muse
Brian Osborne
Bill Piel
Sergei Kosakovsky Pond
Art Poon
Samantha Price
Weigang Qiu
Mark Schreiber

University of Cambridge
NESCent
Duke University
Duke University
Osaka University
Florida State University
European Bioinformatics Institution
University of California – Davis
University of Tokyo
NESCent
University of Connecticut
GlaxoSmithKline
North Carolina State University
NESCent
Yale University
University of California – San Diego
University of California – San Diego
NESCent
Hunter College CUNY
Novartis Institute for Tropical Diseases

Jason Stajich
Arlin Stoltzfus
David Swofford
Tobias Thierer
Albert Vilella
Todd Vision
Rutger Vos
Christian Zmasek
Derrick Zwickl

University of California – Berkeley
University of Maryland, NIST
Florida State University
Biomatters, Inc.
European Bioinformatics Institute
NESCent
University of British Columbia
Burnham Institute
NESCent

May 16 – 17, 2007

**Data Preservation, Sharing, and Discovery: Small
Science in the Digital Era**

**Coordinators: Hilmar Lapp
Todd Vision**

Participants:

Bradley Anholt
Ahrash Bissell
Amy Bouck
Leesa Brieger
Sarah Carrier
Jed Dube
Laura Gasaway
Jane Greenberg
Harold Heatwole
Brad Hemminger
Paul Jones
Joel Kingsolver
Hilmar Lapp
Karen Letart
John Madden
Kristin Martin
Steve Morris
Michael Nelson
Bob Peet
Mark Rausher
Oya Rieger
Dav Robertson
Ryan Scherle
Kathleen Smith
Gail Steinhard
Helen Tibbo
Marcy Uyenoyama
Todd Vision
Stuart Weibel
Derek Wildman

University of Victoria
Duke University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
RENCI
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
North Carolina State University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
NESCent
North Carolina State University
Duke University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
North Carolina State University
Old Dominion University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
Duke University
Cornell University
NIEHS
Indiana University
Duke University
Cornell University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
Duke University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
Online Computer Library Center
Wayne State University

Informatics Courses

July 9 – 19, 2007

Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course
Coordinators: Hilmar Lapp
William Piel

Participants:

Jason Bond	East Carolina University
Joseph Brown	University of Michigan
Karen Cransten	University of Arizona
Kirstin Fisher	NESCent
Josh Granek	Duke University
Einat Hazkani-Covo	NESCent
Colleen Ingram	American Museum of Natural History
Kathleen Kay	University of California – Berkeley
David Kidd	NESCent
Francesc Lopez Giraldez	Yale University
David Maddison	University of Arizona
Jonathan Marcot	University of Colorado
Jenna Morgan	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
Shelah Morita	North Carolina State University
Ahmed Moustafa	University of Iowa
Spencer Muse	North Carolina State University
Amy Non	University of Florida
Jeff Oliver	University of Arizona
Bill Piel	Yale University
Sergei Pond	University of California – San Diego
Amy Powell	Duke University
Santiago Ramirez	Harvard University
Sushma Reddy	Field Museum of Natural History
Cohen Shirley	
Stephen Smith	Yale University
Libby Snell	University of Oxford
Jason Stajich	University of California – Berkeley
Taika von Konigslow	University of Guelph
Rutger Vos	University of British Columbia
Tamaki Yuri	University of Florida

August 16 – 17, 2007

Google Summer of Code End of Summer Meeting
Coordinator: Hilmar Lapp

Participants:

Lars Barquist	Rutgers University – New Brunswick
Jason Caravas	Wayne State University
James Estill	University of Georgia
Ian Holmes	University of California – Berkeley
Gregory Jordan	Yale University

David Kidd
Hilmar Lapp
Bohyun Lee
Michael Nowak
Hisanaga Okada
William Piel
Weigang Qiu
Yi-Hsin Erica Tsai
Todd Vision
Derrick Zwickl

NESCent
NESCent
Georgia Institute of Technology
Duke University
Simon Fraser University
Yale University
Hunter College
Duke University
NESCent
NESCent

Advisory

February 1-2, 2007

Participants:

Stan Blum
Troy Day
Lisa Donovan
Jonathan Eisen
Fred Gould
Catherine Graham
Elizabeth Hadly
Hopi Hoekstra
Laura Katz
Junhyong Kim
Joel Kingsolver
Hirohisa Kishino
Jonathan Losos
Joe Neigel
Sally Otto
William Piel
Judy Plesset
Bruce Rannala
Kathleen Smith
Jeffery Todd Streebman
Paul Turner
Peter Wagner
Peter Wainwright
Katherine Willis
Marlene Zuk

Scientific Advisory Board

Coordinator: Joel Kingsolver

California Academy of Sciences
Queens University
University of Georgia
University of California – Davis
North Carolina State University
State University of New York, Stony Brook
Stanford University
University of California – San Diego
Smith College
University of Pennsylvania
NESCent
University of Tokyo
Washington University in St. Louis
University of Louisiana
University of British Columbia
Yale University
National Science Foundation
University of California – Davis
NESCent
Georgia Institute of Technology
Yale University
The Field Museum
University of California
University of Oxford
University of California – Riverside

August 23 – 24, 2007

**NESCent Senior Advisory Board Meeting
Coordinator: Kathleen Smith**

Participants:

Judy Diamond *	University of Nebraska State Museum
Scott Edwards *	Harvard University
David Hillis	University of Texas – Austin
Ray Huey	University of Washington
David Jablonski	University of Chicago
Elizabeth Kellogg	University of Missouri – St. Louis
Lisa Nagy	University of Arizona
Rod Page	University of Glasgow
Jonathan Prichard *	University of Chicago
Jim Reichman	University of California – Santa Barbara
Barbara Schaal	Washington University – St. Louis
Simon Tavaré *	University of Southern California

*Members not present but participating in written report.

Appendix III.7.

Participant Lists – NESCent Other Supported Activities With Provost Discretionary Funds

December 1, 2006 – November 30, 2007

Co-Supported Meetings

March 19 – 20, 2007

**NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for
Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood
Density Meeting, Group 1 (27A)**
Coordinator: Amy Zanne

Participants:

Jerome Chave
David Coomes
Steven Jansen
Nate Swenson
Mark Westoby
Ian Wright
Amy Zanne
Peter Reich

Université Paul Sabatier
University of Cambridge
Royal Botanical Gardens, Kew
University of Arizona
Macquarie University
Macquarie University
NESCent
University of Minnesota

March 21 – 22, 2007

**NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for
Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood
Density Meeting, Group 2 (27B)**
Coordinator: Amy Zanne

Participants:

Jerome Chave
David Coomes
Steven Jansen
Nate Swenson
Mark Westoby
Ian Wright
Amy Zanne
David Ackerly
Pieter Baas
Edward Davis
Brian Enquist
Rob Jackson

Université Paul Sabatier
University of Cambridge
Royal Botanical Gardens, Kew
University of Arizona
Macquarie University
Macquarie University
NESCent
University of California – Berkeley
Leiden University
University of California – Berkeley
University of Arizona
Duke University

David Kidd
Scott Loarie
Josh Madin
Paul Manos
Jeff Ott
Peter Stevens
Cam Webb
Elisabeth Wheeler
Justin Wright

NESCent
Duke University
NCEAS
Duke University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of Missouri – St. Louis
Harvard University
North Carolina State University
Duke University

March 23 – 24, 2007

**NESCent/ARC-NZ Research Network for
Vegetation Function Wood Anatomy and Wood
Density Meeting, Group 3 (27C)
Coordinator: Amy Zanne**

Participants:

David Coomes
Steven Jansen
Nate Swenson
Mark Westoby
Ian Wright
Amy Zanne
Pieter Baas
Rob Jackson
Josh Madin
Elisabeth Wheeler
Tim Bleby
Vincent Chiang
Brendan Choat
JC Domec
Uwe Hacke
Anna Jacobsen
Cindi Jones
John Sperry

University of Cambridge
Royal Botanical Gardens, Kew
University of Arizona
Macquarie University
Macquarie University
NESCent
Leiden University
Duke University
NCEAS
North Carolina State University
Duke University
North Carolina State University
University of California – Davis
Oregon State University
University of Alberta
Michigan State University
University of Connecticut
University of Utah

Triangle Working Group Meetings

December 17 – 19, 2006

Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression

Coordinators: Marcy Uyenoyama

Alade Tokuta

Rasmus Nielsen

Participants:

David Adeyemi
Yingjun Cao
Ganesh Ganapathy

North Carolina Central University
North Carolina Central University
NESCent

Jody Hey
Asger Hobolth
Scotland Leman
Yi-Ju Li
Carlos Machado
Thomas Mitchell-Olds
Richard Morris
Rasmus Nielsen
Mohamed Noor
Benjamin Redelings
Raazesh Sainudiin
Alade Tokuta
Marcy Uyenoyama
John Willis
Anne Yoder
Ruriko Yoshida
Derrick Zwickl

Rutgers University
North Carolina State University
Duke University
Duke University
University of Arizona
Duke University
Duke University
University of Copenhagen
Duke University
North Carolina State University
Oxford University
North Carolina Central University
Duke University
Duke University
Duke University
University of Kentucky
NESCent

April 14, 2007

**Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular
Biology and Paleontology**

Coordinators: Julia Clarke

Nathalie Nagalingum

Brian Wiegmann

Participants:

Matt Bertone
Joe Carter
Sang-Chul Choi
Julia Clarke
Drew Eddy
Mia Feng
Pat Gensel
Linn Groenveld
A.J. Harris
Nathalie Nagalingum
Mike Nowak
Sam Price
Morgan Raley
Ben Redeling
Eric Schueltpeltz
Mary Schweitzer
Adam Smith
David Thomas
Jeff Thorne
Michelle Trautwein
David Weisrock

North Carolina State University
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Duke University
North Carolina State University
Duke University
Duke University
NESCent
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
Duke University
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
Duke University
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
Duke University

Brian Wiegmann
Jenny Xiang
Wenheng Zhang
Derrick Zwickl

North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
NESCent

Education Course

July 9 – 13, 2007

**NESCent Teacher Education Program: Teaching
An Elementary Story of Life: The Web of Biology,
Ecology and Evolution
Coordinator: Joseph Fail**

Participants:

DeAnna Bray
Emily Day
Jerri Decker
Michelle Ellis
Kala Gonsler
Lorrie Johnson
Molly Jones
Rachel Joyner
Louise Moore
Amber O'Neal
Marion Patterson
Loretta Pizzutilla
Rupa Ray
Kathy Shelton
Rita Singh
Mary Vinson

Hallyburton Elementary
Rashkis Elementary
Sterling Montessori
Lingerfeldt Elementary
Estes Hills Elementary
Draper Elementary
Bonlee Elementary School
Grandy Primary School
Parkway School
Grandy Primary School
Forest View Elementary
Chicod School
Duke University
Lincoln Elementary
Mary Scroggs Elementary School
Hollister Elementary School

Appendix III.8.

Participant Lists – Other Meetings Held at NESCent Not Funded by NESCent

December 1, 2006 – November 30, 2007

January 4 – 6, 2007

Evolution of Function-Valued Traits
Coordinator: Pat Carter

Participants:

Richard Gomulkiewicz
Patrick Carter
Jay Beder
George Gilchrist
Nancy Heckman
Joel Kingsolver
Mark Kirkpartick
Steve Marron
Scott Pletcher
Johanna Schmitt
Rima Izem
David Houle
John Stinchcombe
Cort Griswold
Travis Gaydos
Karin Meyer
Jen Knies
Christina Burch
Greg Ragland
Luke Hoekstra

Washington State University
Washington State University
University of Wisconsin – Milwaukee
College of William and Mary
University of British Columbia
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of Texas – Austin
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
Baylor College of Medicine
Brown University
Harvard University
Florida State University
University of Toronto, Canada
Washington State University
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of New England, Australia
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
College of William and Mary

January 12 – 14, 2007

Evolutionary Editorial Board Meeting
Coordinator: Andrea Macaluso

Participants:

Mark Johnston
Aris Katzourakis
Ellen Larsen
Rebecca German
V. Louise Roth
Kathleen Smith
Russell Tuttle
Miriam Zelditch

Dalhousie University
University of Oxford
University of Toronto
Johns Hopkins University
Duke University
Duke University
University of Chicago
University of Michigan

Benedikt Hallgrímsson
Andrea Macaluso
Kate Davis
Lisa Tenaglia

University of Calgary
Springer
Springer
Springer

January 15 – 16, 2007

**National Science Foundation Site Visit
Coordinator: NSF**

Participants:

James Beach
Jack Hayes
John Huelsenback
Cari Soderlund
David Stern
Chung-I Wu

University of Kansas
University of Nevada – Reno
University of California – Berkeley
Arizona University
Princeton University
University of Chicago

March 17, 2007

**Society for Systematic Biologists Executive Board
Coordinator: Chris Simon**

Participants:

Keith Crandall
Scott Edwards
Vicki Funk
David Mindell
David Penny
Chris Simon
George Weiblen
Kelly Zamudio

Brigham Young University

University of Michigan
Massey University
University of Connecticut
University of Minnesota

April 19 – 20, 2007

**AToL/CBOL Meeting: “Integrating the Tree and
Barcodes of Life”
Coordinator: David Schindel**

Participants:

Bernie Ball
Paul Barber
Meredith Blackwell
Ann Bucklin
Pauly Cartwright
Joel Cracraft
Cliff Cunningham
Chuck Delwiche
Rob DeSalle
Michael Donoghue
Amy Driskell

Duke University
Boston University
Louisiana State University
University of Connecticut
University of Kansas
American Museum of Natural History
Duke University
University of Maryland
American Museum of Natural History
Yale University
Smithsonian Institution

Doug Eernisse
Daphne Fautin
Scott Federhen
Katie Ferrell
Gonzalo Giribet
Fred Grassle
Shannon Hackett
Bob Hanner
Miranda Haskins
David Hillis
Laura Katz
Junhyong Kim
Nancy Knowlton
John Kress
Rich Mayden
Charles Mitter
Steven Nadler
Nathalie Nagalingum
Guillermo Orti
Kathryn Perez
Bill Piel
Sujeevan Ratnasingham
Tatiana Rynearson
Gary Saunders
David Schindel
Jon Shaw
Jim Staley
Simon Tillier
Rytas Vilgalys
Todd Vision
Alfried Vogler
Rachel Whitaker
Suzanne Williams
Gert Worheide

NESCent
University of Kansas
National Center for Biotechnology Information
Smithsonian Institution
Harvard University
Rutgers University
The Field Museum
University of Guelph
Saint Louis University
University of Texas – Austin
Smith College
University of Pennsylvania
University of California – Sand Diego
Smithsonian Institution
Saint Louis University
University of Maryland
University of California – Davis
Duke University
University of Nebraska – Lincoln
Duke University
Yale University
University of Guelph
University of Rhode Island
University of New Brunswick
Smithsonian Institution
Duke University
University of Washington
Museum National D'Histoire Naturelle, France
Duke University
NESCent
Natural History Museum, London
University of Illinois – Urbana-Champaign
Natural History Museum, London
University of Göttingen

April 24 – 27, 2007

**Toward an international exchange standard for
vegetation and biodiversity co-occurrence data
Coordinator: Bob Peet**

Participants:

Matt Bolton

Brad Boyle
Miquel Cáceras
Jerry Cooper
Stephan Hennekens

Department of the Environment and Water
Resources
University of Arizona
Universitat de Barcelona, Spain
Landcare Research, New Zealand
Alterra, Wageningen, The Netherlands

Matt Jones
Martin Kleikamp
Michael Lee
Robert Peet
Kristin Snow
Nick Spencer
Susan Wisner

NCEAS
Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
NatureServe
Landcare Research, New Zealand
Landcare Research, New Zealand

May 30 – 31, 2007

**Ecological Society of America
Coordinator: Cliff Duke**

Participants:

Richard O'Grady
Chip Leslie
Michael Whitlock
Patricia Morse
Reed Beaman
Shan Duncan
Charles Fox
Jonathan Duncan

Jerome Reichman
Kristin Brugger
Cliff Duke
David Baldwin
Jennifer Riem
Mindy Destro
Juan Nunez Farfan

Jenny Talbot
Tom Moritz
Bill Michener
Greg Riccardi
Katja Seltmann
Kathie Hodge
Jim Reichman

Hilmar Lapp
Kathleen Smith
Todd Vision
Wayne Litaker

Bruce Dancik
Peter McCartney
Sam Scheiner
Bob Cook

American Institute of Biological Sciences
American Society of Mammalogists
American Society of Naturalists
American Society of Naturalists
American Society of Plant Taxonomists
Animal Behavior Society
British Ecological Society
Consortium of Universities for the
Advancement of the Hydrologic Science
Duke University Law School
Dupont Crop Protection Products
Ecological Society of America
Ecological Society of America
Ecological Society of America
Ecological Society of America
Ecological Society of Mexico/Federation of the
Americas
ESA Student Section
Getty Research Institute
Long Term Ecological Research Network
MorphBank
MorphBank
Mycological Society of America
National Center for Ecological Analysis and
Synthesis
NESCent
NESCent
NESCent
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration
National Research Council, Canada
National Science Foundation
National Science Foundation
Oak Ridge National Laboratory

Ahrash Bissel
Nora Bynum
Harold Heatwole
Paul Uhlir
Bill Piel
Sarah Carrier
Hal Balbach

Greg Riccardi
Liz Sellers

Bob Peet
Dennis Stevenson

Duke/Alexandria Archive Institute/Open Context
Society for Conservation Biology
Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology
The National Academies
TreeBase
UNC Metadata Research Center
US Army Engineer Research and Development
Center
MorphBank
USGS National Biological Information
Infrastructure
VegBank
Willi Hennig Society

September 10 – 12, 2007

**Processing PhyloData (pPOD): Core Database
Technologies to Enable the Integration of AToL
Information
Coordinator: Val Tannen**

Participants:

Zhuowei Bao
Reed Beaman
Shawn Bowers

University of Pennsylvania
Yale University/University of Florida
University of California - Davis

Peter Buneman
Jonathan Coddington
Susan Davidson
Todd J. Green
Zack Ives
Seth Kaufman
Greg Karvounarakis
Junhyong Kim
Hilmar Lapp
Jim Leebens-Mack
Betram Ludaescher
Francois Lutzoni
David Maddison
Wayne Maddison
Austin Mast
Tim McPhillips
Brent Mishler
Maureen O'Leary
Bill Piel
Greg Riccardi
Val Tannen

University of Edinburgh
Smithsonian Institution
University of Pennsylvania
University of Pennsylvania
University of Pennsylvania
MorphoBank
University of Pennsylvania
University of Pennsylvania
NESCent
University of Georgia
University of California - Davis
Duke University
University of Arizona
University of British Columbia
Florida State University
University of California - Davis
University of California - Berkeley
Stony Brook University
Yale University
Florida State University
University of Pennsylvania

Nick Taylor
David Thau
Todd Vision
Rutger Vos

University of Pennsylvania
University of California - Davis
University of North Carolina – Chapel Hill
University of British Columbia

September 17 – 18, 2007

PhenoMaP Needs Analysis Workshop
Coordinators: Paula Mabee
Todd Vision

Participants:

Arhat Abzhanov
Jim Balhoff
Vasila Dahdul
Jim Hanken
Hopi Hoekstra
Hans Hofmann
Elizabeth Jockusch
Toby Kellogg
Chuck Kimmel
Hilmar Lapp
John Lunberg
Paula Mabee
Peter Midford
Gavin Naylor
David Stern
Todd Vision
Gunter Wagner
Monte Westerfield
Xiaorong Xiang

Harvard University
NESCent
Academy of Natural Sciences
Harvard University
Harvard University
University of Texas – Austin
University of Connecticut
University of Missouri – St. Louis
University of Oregon
NESCent
Academy of Natural Sciences
University of South Dakota
University of British Columbia
Florida State University
Princeton University
NESCent
Yale University
University of Oregon
NESCent

October 5 – 6, 2007

Mimulus FIBR Meeting
Coordinator: John Willis

Participants:

Amy Angert
Camille Barr
Magdalena Bartkowska
Amy Bouck
Toby Bradshaw
Dave Carr
Andrea Case
Charles Chen
Arielle Cooley
Katie Ferris
Lila Fishman

University of Arizona
University of Montana
Dalhousie
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
University of Washington
University of Virginia
Kent State University
University of British Columbia
Duke University
Duke University
University of Montana

Eric Floro	Kent State University
Eric Ganko	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Nick Griffin	Washington University - St. Louis
Dena Grossenbacher	University of California - Davis
Jon Haloin	University of California - Davis
Yujun Han	University of Georgia
Dawn Holligan	University of Georgia
Chris Ivey	California State University - Chico
Young Wha Lee	Duke University
Deborah Lloyd	University of Exeter
David Lowry	Duke University
Mark Macnair	University of Exeter
Jen Modliszewski	Duke University
Courtney Murren	College of Charleston
Arpiar Saunders	University of Montana
Doug Schemske	Michigan State University
Jason Sexton	University of California - Davis
Jay Sobel	Michigan State University
Matt Streisfeld	Duke University
Andrea Sweigart	University of Rochester
Jeff Tomkins	Clemson University
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
John Willis	Duke University
Kevin Wright	Duke University
Carrie Wu	Duke University

Appendix III.9.a.

Year 3 Awards

Appendix III.9.b.

Post Doctoral Fellows

Appendix III.9.c.

Sabbatical Scholars

Appendix III.9.d.

Catalysis and Working Group Totals

**Catalysis and Working Group Totals - Ethnicity
Year 3**

Appendix III.9.e.

Informatics

Appendix III.9.f.

Other Groups

Other Groups - Ethnicity Year 3

Appendix III.9.g.

Home Institution Type – Participants in NESCent Meetings

Appendix III.10.a.

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by State
Year 3

State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total
Alabama	0	1	1	Illinois	6	14	20	North Carolina	70	103	173	Rhode Island	2	0	2
Arizona	3	14	17	Indiana	0	2	2	Nebraska	1	1	2	South Carolina	0	2	2
California	19	44	63	Kansas	2	1	3	New Hampshire	0	3	3	Tennessee	0	1	1
Colorado	3	4	7	Kentucky	1	0	1	New Jersey	1	4	5	Texas	1	12	13
Connecticut	5	26	31	Louisiana	1	3	4	New Mexico	3	4	7	Utah	1	3	4
Washington DC	6	10	16	Massachusetts	7	13	20	Nevada	0	1	1	Virginia	1	8	9
Florida	5	11	16	Maryland	1	11	12	New York	9	24	33	Vermont	1	0	1
Georgia	2	12	14	Maine	1	2	3	Ohio	0	2	2	Washington	1	10	11
Hawaii	3	3	6	Michigan	3	10	13	Oklahoma	0	3	3	Wisconsin	1	5	6
Iowa	1	4	5	Minnesota	3	7	10	Oregon	3	2	5	Wyoming	0	1	1
Idaho	0	1	1	Missouri	3	6	9	Pennsylvania	1	12	13	Totals	171	400	571

Appendix III.10.b.

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by State
Years 1-3

State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total	State	Female	Male	Total
Alabama	0	1	1	Indiana	0	2	2	New Hampshire	0	4	4	South Dakota	4	1	5
Arizona	5	16	21	Kansas	3	4	7	New Jersey	2	7	9	Tennessee	0	2	2
California	31	65	96	Kentucky	1	0	1	New Mexico	3	5	8	Texas	3	16	19
Colorado	3	7	10	Louisiana	1	9	10	Nevada	0	1	1	Utah	1	3	4
Connecticut	5	33	38	Massachusetts	8	19	27	New York	17	37	54	Virginia	2	9	11
Washington DC	7	13	20	Maryland	2	14	16	Ohio	0	10	10	Vermont	1	0	1
Florida	6	19	25	Maine	1	2	3	Oklahoma	0	3	3	Washington	1	10	11
Georgia	4	16	20	Michigan	3	12	15	Oregon	5	5	10	Wisconsin	1	5	6
Hawaii	3	3	6	Minnesota	3	8	11	Pennsylvania	3	19	22	Wyoming	0	2	2
Iowa	2	7	9	Missouri	7	14	21	Puerto Rico	1	3	4	Totals	233	568	801
Idaho	2	5	7	North Carolina	83	130	213	Rhode Island	2	0	2				
Illinois	6	24	30	Nebraska	1	1	2	South Carolina	0	2	2				

Appendix III.10.c

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by Country Year 3

Country	Female	Male	Total	Country	Female	Male	Total
Australia	1	7	8	Netherlands	0	3	3
Brazil	1	0	1	New Zealand	1	4	5
Canada	10	23	33	Norway	0	2	2
Denmark	0	2	2	Singapore	0	1	1
France	1	4	5	Spain	0	1	1
Germany	3	4	7	Sweden	1	0	1
Indonesia	0	1	1	Switzerland	0	2	2
Italy	0	2	2	UK	4	23	27
Japan	0	4	4	US	171	400	571
Mexico	0	2	2	Non-US	22	85	107
				Total	193	485	678

Appendix III.10.d

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by Country Years 1-3

Country	Female	Male	Total	Country	Female	Male	Total	Country	Female	Male	Total
Australia	1	7	8	Israel	0	1	1	Portugal	0	1	1
Brazil	1	0	1	Italy	0	2	2	Singapore	0	1	1
Canada	12	28	40	Jamaica	0	1	1	Spain	0	1	1
Dominican Republic	0	1	1	Japan	0	6	6	Sweden	1	1	2
Denmark	0	2	2	Madagascar	0	1	1	Switzerland	0	2	2
Finland	0	1	1	Mexico	0	2	2	The Netherlands	0	1	1
France	3	6	9	Netherlands	0	3	3	UK	6	27	33
Germany	3	5	8	New Zealand	1	4	5	US	233	568	801
Indonesia	0	1	1	Norway	0	2	2	Non-US	28	108	136
				Panama	0	1	1	Totals	240	602	842

Appendix III.11.

Current NESCent Meetings Expected for Program Year 4
(December 1, 2007 – November 30, 2008)

Lastname	Firstname	Group Type	Meeting Title
Bergman,	Casey	Working Group	Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution.
Buckley	Lauren	Working Group	Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, and Population Dynamics
Clarke	Julia	Triangle Working Group	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology
Cracraft,	Joel	Working Group	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography
Donoghue	Michael	Working Group	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere
Donovan	Sam	NESCent EOG	EOG TREE
Forde	Samantha	Working Group	Models, Microbes and Evolutionary Diversification
Gould	Fred	Catalysis Group	Selfish DNA and the genetic control of vector-borne diseases
Jungck	John	Working Group	Synergistic Evolutionary Learning Consortium: Evolution in ACTION
Kozak	Kenneth	Working Group	Montane Diversity in Space and Time
Lahti	David	Working Group	Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution
Leebens-Mack	Jim	Working Group	The Plant EvoGenetics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics
Magwene	Paul	Working Group	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks
Noor	Mohamed	Working Group	Proposal to Develop a Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses
Nunn	Charles	Working Group	How Does Cognition Evolve?
Oakley	Todd	Working Group	Fossil and Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times for the Tree of Life: Database and Synthesis
Payne	Jonathan	Working Group	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology
Stoltzfus	Arlin	Working Group	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis
Strier	Karen	Working Group	Primate Life Histories
Uno	Gordon	NESCent EOG	Evolution Across the Curriculum
Uyenoyama	Marcy	Triangle Working Group	Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression

Appendix III.12.

NESCent Representation at Meetings December 1, 2006 – November 30, 2007

Outreach Activities by NESCent Directors and Staff

Kathleen Smith

- Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, January 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- Society for the Study of Evolution, Christchurch, New Zealand, June 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- International Congress of Vertebrate Morphology, Paris France, July 2007 (Poster)
- SACNAS, Kansas City, Participant in NESCent EOG Activities, October 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- Society for Vertebrate Paleontology, Austin Texas, October 2007
- National Association of Biology Teachers, Atlanta, GA, November 27-December 2, 2007 (NESCent Booth)

Joel Kingsolver

- NOAA Fisheries Symposium and Workshop: Evolutionary Responses to Environmental Change in Salmon, Seattle, WA December 7-9, 2006
- European Science Foundation Workshop: Thermal Adaptation in Ectotherms, Barcelona, Spain, March 15-17, 2007

Todd Vision

- Plant Biology and Botany 2007 Joint Congress: Annual Meetings of the American Fern Society (AFS), American Society of Plant Biologists (ASPB), American Society of Plant Taxonomists (ASPT), and Botanical Society of American (BSA), July 7-11, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, Halifax, Nova Scotia, June 24-28, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- Discussed GMOD and Genome Database Infrastructure Needs with Evolutionary Model Organism Community, Boston, MA, May 18-19, 2007

Hilmar Lapp

- Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology Conference 2007 (ISMB 2007), Vienna, Austria, July 21-25, 2007
- Open Repositories 2007, San Antonio, TX, January 22-26, 2007
- Society of Molecular Biology and Evolution Annual Meeting 2007 (SMBE 2007), Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada, June 22-29, 2007 (NESCent Booth)

Greg Gibson

- American Genetics Association, IN, July, 2007

Kristin Jenkins

- *Evolution: Education & Outreach* (new journal), Springer Editorial Board Meeting, New Orleans, LA, March 2-4, 2007
- AIBS Annual Meeting, Washington, DC, May 13-16, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- 2007 Plant Biology and Botany Congress, Chicago, IL, July 6-11, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- North Carolina Science Teachers Association, Greensboro, NC, November 14-16, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- National Association of Biology Teachers, Atlanta, GA, November 27-December 2, 2007 (NESCent Booth)

Jory Weintraub

- *Evolution: Education & Outreach* (new journal), Springer Editorial Board Meeting, New Orleans, LA, March 2-4, 2007
- AIBS 2007 Annual Meeting, Washington, DC, May 13-15, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- BioQUEST, Selection Working Group, Beloit College, Beloit, WI, June 9-13, 2007
- SACNAS Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science, Kansas City, MO, October 10-14, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- North Carolina Science Teachers Association, Greensboro, NC, November 14-16, 2007 (NESCent Booth)
- National Association of Biology Teachers, Atlanta, GA, November 27-December 2, 2007 (NESCent Booth)

Participation in Scientific Meetings by NESCent Scientists

Jim Balhoff

- 2nd International Biocuration Meeting, San Jose, CA, October 2007
- Phenotype and Trait Ontology Workshop related to CTOL, Stanford University, CA, November 2006

Surya Dhullipalla

- SMBE Annual Meeting, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada, June 24-28, 2007

Ganesh Ganapathy

- SMBE 2007, Halifax, Nova Scotia, June 2007

Einat Hazkani-Covo

- The Biology of Genomes, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, NY, May 2007
- SMBE 2007, Halifax, Nova Scotia, June 2007

Jason Hoeksema

- NCEAS Working Group: Bridging the Gap Between Theory and Practice in Mycorrhizal Management, Santa Barbara, CA, April 16, 2007

Samantha Hopkins

- Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology, Phoenix, AZ January 3-7, 2007
- American Society of Mammalogists Mtg., June 7-11, 2007

David Kidd

- 3rd International Biogeography Society Conference, Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain, January 9-13, 2007
- Biogeographically-based Integrative Historical and Ecological Science: Grand Collaborative Studies of Whole Biotas, PI Brett Riddle, Cliff Cunningham, Michael Donoghue and Anne Yoder, Las Vegas, NV, May 17-20, 2007
- 6th Biennial Systematics Association Meeting 28th 31st August 2007, Royal Botanical Gardens Edinburgh, UK Edinburgh, St. Andrews, London, Portsmouth and beyond, August 25-October 11, 2007

Xianhua Liu

- SMBE Annual Meeting, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada, June 24-28, 2007

Lauren McCall

- International Society for the History, Philosophy and Social Studies of Biology, University of Essex, UK, July 23-30, 2007

Brian Sidlauskas

- American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists, St. Louis, MO, July 11-17, 2007

Amy Zanne

- Association for Tropical Biology and Conservation Annual Meeting, El Eden, Mexico, July 5-19, 2007

Derrick Zwickl

- Annual Meeting of the Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, June 24-29, 2007
- Workshop on Molecular Evolution, Marine Biological Laboratories, Woods Hole, MA, July 29-August 7, 2007

Appendix III.13.

NESCent Call for Proposals

Announcement Sent to the Following Web Site sand List Serves

1. American Ornithological Union (AOU)
2. American Physiological Society – Comparative & Evolutionary Physiology Section (APS – CEPS)
3. American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists (ASIH)
4. American Society of Mammalogists (ASM)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
5. Animal Behavior Society (ABS)
6. BIRDNET web site
7. Botanical Society of America (BSA)
8. EvolDir - Evolution Directory (EvolDir)
9. Evolution and Medicine web site
10. Genetics Society of America (GSA)
11. Geological Society of America
12. Paleobotany list serve (through Pat Gensel)
13. Paleontological Society web site
14. Society of Developmental Biology (SDB)
15. Society for Integrative & Comparative Biology (SICB)
16. Society of Molecular Biology and Evolution (SMBE)
17. Society for Study of Evolution (SSE)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
18. Society of Systematic Biology (SSB)
19. Society for Vertebrate Paleontology (SVP)

APPENDIX IV.2

Abstract of Lapp et al. manuscript describing the 2006 NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon, accepted pending revision at Evolutionary Bioinformatics.

The 2006 NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon: A Field Report

In December, 2006, a group of 26 software developers from some of the most widely used life science programming toolkits and phylogenetic software projects converged on Durham, North Carolina, for a Phyloinformatics Hackathon, an intense five-day collaborative software coding event sponsored by the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (NESCent). The goal was to help researchers to integrate multiple phylogenetic software tools into automated workflows. Participants addressed the lack of interoperability between programs by implementing "glue code" and improving support for phylogenetic data exchange standards (particularly NEXUS) across the toolkits. The work was guided by use-cases compiled in advance by both developers and users, and the code was documented as it was developed. The resulting software is freely available for both users and developers through incorporation into the distributions of several widely-used open-source toolkits. We explain the motivation for the hackathon, how it was organized, and discuss some of the outcomes and lessons learned. We conclude that hackathons are an effective mode of solving problems in software interoperability and usability, and are underutilized in scientific software development.

APPENDIX IV.3

“Data Preservation, Sharing, and Discovery: Challenges for Small Science in the Digital Era”, a report of a workshop held May 16 -17th 2007 at NESCent.

Sponsors: NESCent and the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill School of Information and Library Science Metadata Research Center (<MRC>)

Project leaders: Jane Greenberg (MRC), Hilmar Lapp (NESCent) and Todd Vision (NESCent).

Participants: Participants included project participants from the NESCent-MRC digital data sharing initiative, representatives from major evolutionary biology journals and societies, and experts from the information, library and computer science communities.

Representatives and trainees from MRC & SILS

- MRC-associated students and postdocs: Amy Bouck, Sarah Carrier, Jed Dube
- SILS students: Lori Eakin, Carolyn Hank, Laura Sheble
- Helen Tibbo, University of North Carolina Chapel Hill

Representatives from NESCent, journals and scientific societies

- Bradley Anholt, U. of Victoria/Journal of Evolutionary Biology
- Ahrash Bissell, Duke U./OpenContext
- Harold Heatwole, NCSU/Editor of Integrative and Comparative Biology
- Joel Kingsolver, UNC Chapel Hill/NESCent/American Society of Naturalists
- Mark Rausher, Duke University/Editor of Evolution
- Loren Rieseberg, U. British Columbia/Editor of Molecular Ecology (participating by conference call)
- Kathleen Smith, Duke University/NESCent
- Marcy Uyenoyama, Duke U./Editor of Molecular Biology and Evolution

Representatives from Information, Library and Computer Science

- Leesa Brieger, Renaissance Computing Institute
- Brad Hemminger, UNC Chapel Hill
- Paul Jones, UNC Chapel Hill/iBiblio
- Karen Letarte, NCSU Libraries
- John Madden, Duke U.
- Kristin Martin, UNC Chapel Hill Libraries
- Steve Morris, NCSU Digital Libraries Initiative
- Michael Nelson, Old Dominion University/Open Archives Institute
- Oya Rieger, Cornell U. Libraries
- David Romito, UNC Chapel Hill Libraries
- Ryan Scherle, Indiana University/NESCent
- Gail Steinhard, Cornell U. Libraries
- Larry Tindell, private contractor/NIEHS
- Stuart Weibel, Online Computer Library Center
- Derek Wildman, Wayne State University, Assistant Editor, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution

Goals:

In “small science” disciplines, such as evolutionary biology, data are typically collected by individual investigators and are highly heterogeneous in content and structure. The nature of these data poses unique challenges to preservation, discovery, sharing and integration. This workshop was intended to help identify the way forward for long-term preservation and sharing of digital datasets that underlie published works in evolutionary biology and other small sciences and inform the future work of DRIADE, the NESCent-MRC data repository project.

Summary of Activities and Discussions:

The meeting opened with a welcome to NESCent and introductions. This was followed by a set of presentations intended to provide background useful for the breakout discussions:

- Todd Vision: Introduction to DRIADE
- Ahrash Bissell: OpenContext and the Alexandria Archive Institute
- Leesa Brieger: SRB & iRODS, Paul Jones: iBiblio.org
- Michael Nelson: OAI and OAI standards
- Oya Rieger: Data Curation and eScholarship
- Gail Steinhart: Integrating discipline-specific metadata standards for digital curation
- Stuart Weibel: OCLC, Identifiers, and the web of the future
- Jane Greenberg: Objectives of the workshop

Four themes were then addressed by individual breakout groups. The breakouts were run concurrently, and the whole set of four breakouts was repeated once, giving each participant the ability to participate in two groups.

1. Adoption and sustainability. How can a repository achieve long-term financial sustainability? What must be done to promote adoption by scientists?
2. Intellectual property. How to balance intellectual property concerns with the goals of data sharing?
3. Distribution and replication. What are the possibilities and liabilities of distributed data management and how can a repository interface with specialized repositories?
4. Lifecycle management. What are the challenges and issues related to a heterogeneous and changing landscape of data formats and technologies?

The workshop closed with a group discussion on “How will emerging technologies (e.g. semantic web/Web 2.0) impact the future of digital data sharing in small science disciplines?” led by a presentation on Web 2.0 technologies by Stu Weibel of OCLC. All discussions were recorded and later summarized in written form by MRC students. Discussion notes and summaries are available from the following URL: https://www.nescent.org/wg_digitaldata/Public:DRIADE_Workshop_May_2007

After general participants departed, a stakeholder discussion was held that included DRIADE personnel (Bouck, Greenberg, Lapp, Smith, Vision) along with editors and society representatives (Anholt, Kingsolver, Uyenoyama, Wildman, Rieseberg [on conf. call]).

Some of the areas of consensus that emerged were as follows:

Sustainability: A disciplinary repository focused on published data needs to include a critical mass of highly respected journals in order to achieve community support and to be financially sustainable. The business model needs to ensure long-term viability, and user trust, and the management structure needs to ensure community oversight and ownership. A variety of financial models are possible, but it was agreed that charging for data access would be fatal to adoption. The effort should also engage students to use shared data and tools and acclimatize them to the culture and value of data sharing.

Policy: Journals will need to take responsibility for author compliance with data sharing policies, and for setting clear policies as to what and how gets deposited, but repositories also need to have human curators in order to check the validity of the submissions and to help users with problems. The policies for data use and citation need to be very clear, and ideally follow the model provided by Creative Commons and Science Commons. Additionally, a data sharing policy must permit exceptions for sensitive data (whether due to privacy, conservation concerns, etc).

Adoption: A catch-all repository needs to exist first before some of the journals will be able to require data sharing of their authors. It is important for community acceptance that there be a way for data to be cited, and for data users to also cite the original publications. It was also agreed that allowing for data embargoes of limited time would assist with acceptance. One-stop data deposition would be a major incentive to researchers, and stakeholders agreed that the first repositories to consider for inclusion would be Genbank, Treebase, possibly repositories for microarray data. The deposition process itself needs to be dead simple. Providing tools and services (for scholarly communication, analysis, etc) on top of the repository will promote adoption (citation counters, format converters, etc). Any system should be designed around the way that researchers currently work – it was pointed out repeatedly that changing a scientific culture is hard. Research

is needed on the motivations and practices of data sharing and withholding in the field of evolutionary biology.

Technical infrastructure: Global, unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers are crucially important for data repositories, but there is not consensus on the appropriate technology. Interoperability of repositories would be greatly enabled by adoption of metadata-harvesting standards (such as OAI-PMH) and the use clearly defined web services (such as SRU). Interoperability with and reuse of the ecoinformatics tools developed by NCEAS should be a high priority. Consideration should be given to long-term preservation technologies and models (e.g. LOCKSS) and repository redundancy. The use of full-text from the article would be valuable for providing contextual metadata – and so getting publishers on board with the idea of allowing selective quoting would be desirable. The repository should aim to capitalize on its unique collection of data to enable Web 2.0 style features. Thought should be given to way that the system could track and take advantage of patterns of user behavior to guide resource discovery and personalize the user interface, for example by providing tag clouds or click statistics.

Follow-up and outcomes

The workshop and its associated planning sessions helped to crystallize a Joint Data Archiving Policy, drafted by sabbatical scholar Michael Whitlock (also the current Editor-in-Chief of the American Naturalist), which reads as follows:

“<<Journal title>> requires, as a condition for publication, that data used in the paper should be archived in an appropriate public archive, such as Genbank, Treebase, or Dryad. The data should be given with sufficient details that, together with the contents of the paper, allows each result in the published paper to be re-created. Authors may elect to have the data publicly available at time of publication, or, if the archive allows, may opt to embargo access to the data for a period up to a year after publication. Exceptions may be granted at the discretion of the editor, especially for sensitive information such as the location of endangered species.”

This policy has been (and is still being) intensively discussed by the officers of scientific societies and journals over the summer.

A major grant proposal for a digital data repository was submitted in July to the National Science Foundation program in Biological Databases and Informatics. The proposal implements many of the ideas that were discussed at the Small Data Workshop. Letters of support were provided from the American Naturalist, Integrative and Comparative Biology, Journal of Evolutionary Biology, Molecular Biology and Evolution, Molecular Ecology, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, and Systematic Biology, and this level of community engagement was made possible, in good measure, by the workshop and surrounding discussions. The proposal, if funded, will allow additional follow-up in the form of community engagement workshops and outreach activities.

APPENDIX IV.4

Summary of proposal submitted to NSF BD&I program in July 2007; **A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology**; PI: K. Smith, co-PIs: K. Antelman, J. Greenberg, W. Michener, W. Piel; Budget: \$2,180,169 (D&I); Duration: 36 months starting 6/1/2008.

The field of evolutionary biology is suffering from a crisis of data attrition. Specialized databases exist for some of the most commonly seen data types, but it is rare that every dataset associated with a published paper has a suitable permanent home. Furthermore, while many evolutionary biology journals have policies that encourage authors to share data, evolutionary biology is typical of many “small science” disciplines in that there are only piecemeal standards, and little infrastructure, that enable authors to do so. At the behest of major journals and societies in evolutionary biology, NESCent has begun development of a digital repository, called Dryad, for the preservation, discovery and sharing of data underlying published works in the field. The overall aim in this proposal is to facilitate data sharing upon publication by the evolutionary community through a myriad of technical and organizational improvements to Dryad, particularly with respect to (1) the deposition and access interface, (2) incentives and interoperability, and (3) sustainability. We will also (4) promote the use Dryad within the research community, and as an educational tool to teach future scientists about the value of digital data archives. The Specific Aims (SA) include the following.

1. Deposition and access interface. [SA1.1] Data deposition will be coordinated with manuscript submission so that reliable bibliographic metadata is automatically captured by Dryad and the identifier for each data object can be transmitted to the journal. [SA1.2] We will study ways to capture more extensive metadata from authors using automatic metadata generation. [SA1.3] To maintain both data integrity and metadata quality, data curators will validate and, if necessary, edit, submissions. [SA1.4] The retrieval interface will structure and augment queries using the scientific metadata coupled with existing and newly developed vocabularies. [SA1.5] Both the fundamental and novel aspects of Dryad will be extensively evaluated and user-tested.

2. Incentives and interoperability. [SA2.1] As proof-of-concept for the idea of “one-stop data deposition”, we will implement hand-shaking mechanisms with two specialized databases (Genbank, for sequence data, and TreeBASE, for phylogenetic data) such that data will simultaneously be deposited in Dryad and the specialized database. [SA2.2] Dryad will assign globally unique, stable, and resolvable identifiers for datasets and promote a convention for the data citations. [SA2.3] Federation of searches across Dryad and other digital collections in biology and beyond will be achieved by implementing the OAI-PMH protocol for metadata harvesting in Dryad, TreeBASE and Metacat, the premier metadata registry and data repository for ecology. [SA2.4] On-the-fly queries, and syndication, of repository contents will be achieved by implementing the SRU/W standards for web services within Dryad and MetaCat.

3. Sustainability. [SA3.1] Dryad will be overseen by a Governing Board (MB) of stakeholders from evolutionary biology journals and societies, advised by information science experts and representatives from other scientific data sharing initiatives, who will set policy and plan for the financial self-sufficiency of the repository beyond the life of this project. [SA3.2] We will explore technical advances in the long-term stewardship of digital data collections by implementing the LOCKSS distributed data preservation system, in addition to managing a more standard architecture of redundant production and backup systems within the North Carolina State University Libraries.

4. Community engagement. [SA4.1] Datasets of special educational value will be targeted and developed for classroom use through a dedicated education section of the repository. [SA4.2] Dryad tutorials will be presented at major evolutionary biology conferences to promote adoption and increase the extent and quality of the metadata provided by authors. [SA4.3] Annual workshops will be held to support emerging metadata and interoperability standards in the field of evolutionary biology, and plan for future handshaking efforts.

The work proposed here will have a broad and transformative impact by enabling the preservation, discovery, sharing and reuse of data for an entire biological discipline. It represents a unique collaboration among diverse institutions (academic journals and associated scientific societies, a national synthesis center and research network, a major community database) and expert communities (evolutionary biologists, information scientists and research librarians). It will serve as a model for the many other “small science” disciplines facing similar challenges in data preservation and sharing.

APPENDIX IV.5.

Summary of proposal submitted to NSF INTEROP program in August 2007; **INTEROP: Creation of a Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences**; PI: W. Michener; co-PIs: M. Jones, K Smith; co-Is: R. Cook, M. Frame, M. Servilla, D. Vieglaiss, T. Vision.

I. Intellectual Merit. The scientific community needs reliable infrastructure that enables open, stable, persistent, robust, and secure access to well-described and logically organized biodiversity, ecological and environmental data. What is needed is a virtual distributed network of data centers that seamlessly supports discovery and user-friendly access to a broad array of data, metadata, and other digital products that are archived securely and permanently in multiple locations. Under this proposal we will develop new community capacity and new technologies to support the design, implementation, and deployment of a Virtual Data Center (VDC) for biodiversity, ecological and environmental data—all founded on open standards and protocols for interoperability among existing and new data centers. Semi-annual week-long meetings of Technical Working Groups (engaging information scientists from data centers representing many diverse disciplines), a developer, and numerous students will contribute to VDC prototypes and adopting and adapting basic system interoperability standards, such as the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting from the digital library community and various scientific community data exchange standards (e.g., SEEK EarthGrid protocols, the oceanographic communities' OPeNDAP protocol, Federal Geographic Data Committee Biological Data Profile, and the web community's grid service protocols).

II. Broader Impacts. An annual meeting of the Community Engagement Working Group (two dozen or more representatives of scientific societies and emerging national and international environmental observatories) plus an annual External Advisory Committee meeting will address socio-cultural barriers to data preservation and data sharing, as well as data center and VDC sustainability. The goal is to design a flexible VDC so that new data centers representing additional disciplines or sub-disciplines, projects, agencies, libraries, or research networks can easily collaborate with the VDC, thereby collectively enhancing overall community capacity and participation. Education and outreach are integral to the project. Four students will participate annually in a summer cyberinfrastructure traineeship that is modeled after the Google Summer of Code™. Additional students will be engaged during the academic year in projects identified by the Working Groups. Outreach will be provided at annual meetings of relevant professional societies, emerging environmental observatories, and research networks. Project results will be incorporated in numerous annual training sessions supported by project partners and through the broad adoption of the interoperability solutions developed as part of this project. In addition to promoting diverse participation in Working Group activities and summer traineeships, results will be freely and openly accessible via the project web site.

APPENDIX IV.6

Summary of award from the NIH Program for Continued Enhancement and Maintenance of Software. **Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser**; PI: I. Holmes, co-PIs: L. Stein, T. Vision. Budget: \$384,000 (to NESCent); Duration: 36 months starting on 4/1/2007.

The Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) software tools comprises a set of biological data management and visualization components suited for creating integrated online databases of genomic data. This proposal seeks to significantly enhance the functionality of one of the most popular of the GMOD tools, the GBrowse genome annotation browser, by giving it smooth scrolling and zooming abilities, as well as a facility for commenting on existing annotations that encourages democratic genome annotation. In recognition of the shift of biology away from the analysis of a single individual and towards the study of whole populations, we also propose to add features that make GBrowse suitable for visualizing genetic association and diversity data. These enhancements will be implemented without destroying the aspects of GBrowse that made it popular in the first place: the ability to install and run it on personal computers and other modest hardware.

This proposal further seeks to encourage the take up by the community of the integrated GMOD suite. While individual components of GMOD have been taken up enthusiastically by the community and are widely used, the full suite of tools, which includes a database schema, a workflow management system, a data mining system and a template-based web site, have not achieved the same penetration due to the lack of comprehensive documentation, packaging and examples. We wish to rectify this situation by establishing a full-time support center responsible for GMOD packaging, documentation, end-user education and outreach.

APPENDIX IV.7

Summary of award from NSF BD&I; **Linking evolution to genomics using phenotype ontologies**; PI: P. Mabee; co-PIs: M. Westerfield, T. Vision; Budget: \$1,050,944 (D&I to NESCent); Duration: 36 months starting 6/01/2007.

The aim of this proposal is to develop tools to integrate evolutionary and model organism phenotype data using ontologies in order to address questions about the genetic and developmental regulation of evolutionary morphological transitions. Specifically, we propose to develop and apply ontologies for taxa and phenotypes in a large clade of fishes (the Ostariophysi) and to develop a suite of database and web-interface tools that will enable researchers to investigate relationships between evolutionary phenotypes and those seen in genetically characterized developmental mutants of zebrafish (a species within Ostariophysi). Combining the wealth of genomic data on the numerous phenotypic mutants for zebrafish, with the span of corresponding anatomical diversity in ostariophysan species will allow researchers to discover previously unrealized connections between evolutionary change, genes, and the developmental processes in which these genes play a role. We will demonstrate the feasibility of our approach by implementing a select number of use-case queries as a proof-of-concept. The queries will be implemented via a web-based user interface for searching and analyzing the data content.

The first goal is to conduct a needs analysis for integration of evolutionary and model organism phenotypes by collaborative development, refinement and prioritization of use cases. Our second goal is to annotate evolutionary phenotypic diversity in a monophyletic group of fishes, the ostariophysans, using anatomical ontologies and standard syntax. We will expand the zebrafish anatomical ontology into a multi-species ontology for their broader lineage, the Ostariophysi. We will extend the Phenotype and Trait Ontology in collaboration with the National Center for Biomedical Ontology. As part of this process, we will store statements of homology between entities, so that individual investigators may select particular relationships based on evidence. We will also develop a taxonomic ontology in order to relate species with particular characters and states. Our third goal is to develop the database and web interface tools to support the research queries desired by the community. EQSYTE (Entity-Quality System for Trait Evolution) will consist of a database and user interface in which the ontologies and data for evolutionary phenotypes are integrated with the zebrafish mutant phenotypes and associated genetic data from ZFIN. Proof-of-concept will be obtained by implementing the use cases developed through the working group.

Intellectual Merit. Representing anatomical character data in an ontology-based framework is a new, forward-looking, and integrative move for phylogenetic systematic studies. The ontologies, which will be developed and shared with model organism databases, will allow immediate integration with genetic and developmental data. Thus, for the first time, research questions can be addressed [using our web-interface and query tools] that require simultaneous data-mining of phylogenetic and genetic data. This approach will also promote integration across morphological systematic studies. Our study, which matches zebrafish model organism genetic data with phylogenetic data from the lineage to which zebrafish belongs (Cypriniformes and ostariophysan relatives), can be generalized to other model organisms and their respective clades. We bring to this study a unique collaboration between evolutionary and model organism biologists that builds upon the strengths of two national centers, a model organism database, a Tree of Life study, a Research Coordination Network, and several community image databases.

Broader Impacts. Ontologies have not previously been used in evolutionary biology, though there is a high level of interest in learning more about their application, logic, and utility. We are proposing educational workshops under the auspices of the National Center for Biomedical Ontology (NCBO). Additionally, participants from the broader community will also be invited to our core workshops at NESCent. We have the support of the fish NSF Research Coordination Network for cross-training students to work in association with informatics personnel. Finally, our database and search engine will foster the integration of the genetics-oriented model organism and evolution communities.

APPENDIX IV.8 NESCENT WEBSITE TRAFFIC

NESCent Website Activity

The NESCent website underwent a major revision and was launched January, 2007. This report reflects activity since then. To increase awareness about the new site, and programs at NESCent, Kathleen Smith sent emails to colleagues from a list of 90 different universities, inviting them to visit our web site, sign up for our newsletter and consider submitting a proposal to NESCent. After each email, we were able to track a cluster of hits from that institution.

In general, the majority of traffic to the site is direct, with the remaining half divided between search engines and referring sites. The highest number of referrals came from the AIBS, UNC, Duke, and Google websites. Additional referrals have come from Slashdot (www.ask.slashdot.com), self described as “News for nerds. Stuff that matters.” and an education resource site at Swarthmore College (<http://swarthmore.edu/NatSci/cpurrin1/evolk12/teaching/resources.htm>).

Total Visitors since January, 2007: 27,150

 Returning Visitors: 14,676 (54.06%)

 New Visitors: 12,474 (45.94%)

Daily Average: 103 Visits / Day

Weekly Average: 715 Visits / Week

Visitor Home Location:

North Carolina (including internal): 12,072
United States (non-North Carolina): 10,342
International: 4,726

Most Frequently Visited Pages:

Education and Outreach Home
Science and Synthesis Home
About NESCent
Awards Page
Informatics Home

APPENDIX V.1 – EOG NATIONAL CONFERENCE ACTIVITIES

The EOG maintained a presence at several national conferences in Year 3.

Conference	Booth	Presentation	Other Comments
AIBS (American Institute of Biological Sciences)	Yes	Yes	Participation in Board and Council meetings and Minority Lunch
Botanical Congress (Botanical Society of America)	Yes	Yes, with BioQUEST	
SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science)	Yes	Yes (Panel discussion on careers in evolution)	Co-sponsored by AIBS
NCSTA (North Carolina Science Teachers Association)	Yes		
NABT (National Association of Biology Teachers)	Yes	Yes	Evolution Symposium (co-sponsored by AIBS, BSCS), CD-ROM produced and distributed

Evolution in the News Podcasts from the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center Project Summary

The National Evolutionary Synthesis Center will produce 15 multimedia podcasts illustrating current research and findings in evolutionary biology. These narratives will focus on important evolutionary concepts and will be bundled with educational materials addressing common misconceptions about that concept. A web based support site for instructors will also be established, and the program will be assessed for effectiveness. This Evolution in the News project will give educators a creative approach to presenting cutting edge research in evolutionary biology, combined with appropriate educational resources, in a format that appeals to undergraduate students. The National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (NESCent) is in a unique position to produce this material because of connections to both the evolutionary research and education communities. Dissemination to a broad audience will occur through iTunes U and the NESCent web site.

Intellectual Merit

Evolution education is important throughout the field of biology for students to gain a thorough understanding of how biological systems, from the molecular to the ecosystem, function individually and interact with one another. Unfortunately, evolution is a contentious topic. Many students hold preconceived ideas about evolution, including misconceptions about basic evolutionary concepts. Students may perceive evolution as stale and outdated, or worse – invalid science. The prevalence of misconceptions about basic evolutionary concepts is staggering, and studies have demonstrated the tenacity of these misconceptions in traditional lecture style learning environments.

To effectively engage students in learning evolution, undergraduate instructors need compelling, interesting and up to date examples of evolution to use in class and an effective method for addressing misconceptions. By demonstrating the relevance of evolutionary biology in students' lives instructors may capture students' interest. Given the interdisciplinary role of evolution, instructors need access to examples across biological fields. Instructors also need educational materials that are based on effective pedagogies to address student misconceptions. The Evolution in the News podcast series will be designed to address the above conceptual and pedagogical issues.

Broader Impact

This project promotes teaching and learning, and reaches a broad audience. Although the project focuses on evolutionary biology, studying evolution is an excellent way to increase students' understanding of the nature of science. That understanding of science transfers across scientific disciplines, contributing to improvement of science education in general. The multimedia approach has been shown to engage a broad range of learning styles, and has benefits for non-traditional students and non-Native English speakers. Distribution of the material via the web takes advantage of technology to transcend geographic barriers, serving both rural and urban groups. This project provides enhanced educational resources and independent professional development for instructors. The product contributes to the generation of a more scientifically literate society.

APPENDIX VI.1

NESCent-supported student projects that were part of the 2007 Google Summer of Code. Additional information, including links to project blogs and where to obtain the open source code, can be found at <http://phylosoc.nescent.org>.

1. A Perl-based Command Line Interface to a Topological Query Application for BioSQL

Student: Jamie Estill (U. Georgia)

Primary mentor: Hilmar Lapp (NESCent)

Abstract: The aim is to create a set of command line programs in Perl for topological queries in BioSQL suitable for high-throughput creation and modification of SQL based phylogenies. This interface will be used to further my research on the classification of plant LTR retrotransposons.

2. Phyloinformatics Web Tools: PhyloSOAP and PhyloWidget

Student: Gregory Jordan (Duke U.)

Primary mentor: Bill Piel (Yale U.)

Abstract: The aim is to (a) create a user-friendly and web-accessible GUI for creating phylogenetic tree queries, and (b) implement a SOAP-based client and server protocol for transmitting phylogenetic queries and results.

3. APIs for BioJava

Student: Bohyun Lee (Georgia Institute of Technology)

Primary mentor: Richard Holland (European Bioinformatics Institute)

Abstract: The aim is to develop APIs in BioJava for phylogeny reconstruction methods (including distance, Maximum Parsimony, and Maximum Likelihood methods)

4. Multi-language bindings to the C++ NEXUS Class Library

Student: Carlos David Suárez Pascal (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México)

Primary mentor: Mark Holder (University of Kansas)

Abstract: The aim is the development of bindings to NCL for three scripting languages (Perl, Python, Ruby) employing SWIG, an open source tool designed to facilitate the development of extensions from C/C++ to another languages. This will provide a way to rapidly prototype and develop applications supporting the NEXUS format.

5. Phylogenetic XML <--> Object serialization

Student: Jason Caravas (Wayne State University)

Primary mentor: Rutger Vos (U. of British Columbia)

Abstract: The aim is to develop an XML based file format for use in phylogenetic analysis. That contains most of the functionality of the current NEXUS file format. Additionally, a parser for this file type is being developed for the BioPerl package.

6. Ajax interface for the XRate command-line tool

Student: Lars Barquist (Rutgers U.)

Primary mentor: Ian Holmes (U. of Berkeley)

Abstract: This project focuses on building an easy-to-use, visual interface for Xrate. It incorporates RNAAV as an alignment viewer, along with the BubblePlot and GraphViz tools for xrate's training mode.

7. Implementing a web interface for command line-based bioinformatics tools

Student: James Leung (U. of Alberta)

Primary mentor: Suzanna Lewis (U. of Berkeley)

Abstract: This project aims to construct a web-based interface for the xrate tool. It is hoped that such an interface will then be portable enough to be used on other similar tools to allow for easy deployment of any command line based bioinformatics utility.

8. Phylogenetic & haplotype displays for GBrowse

Student: Hisanaga Mark Okada (Simon Fraser University)

Primary mentor: Lincoln Stein (Cold Spring Harbor Laboratories)

Abstract: The aim is to modify the GBrowse visualization by dividing the single large image to multiple tracks and add phylogenetic information as a new data track.

9. Estimation of divergence time priors from fossil occurrence data

Student: Michael Nowak (Duke U.)

Primary mentor: Derrick Zwickl (NESCent)

Abstract: The aim is to develop a software tool in C++ for the analysis of fossil occurrence data from the Paleobiology Database, in order to calculate informative priors on divergence times. This is being designed for implementation in the open source Bayesian molecular divergence time package BEAST.

10. Visualizing Phylogeographic Information

Student: Yi-Hsin Erica Tsai (Duke U.)

Mentors: David Kidd (NESCent)

Abstract: This project will develop a web based application that generates geographic maps of DNA haplotype data that are often used in phylogeographic analysis. The application will create maps of pie charts viewable through Google Earth that show the spatial distributions of haplotypes, the frequency of each haplotype within each population, and the number of samples per population.

11. Biodiversity conservation algorithms and GUI

Student: Klaas Hartmann (University of Canterbury, NZ)

Primary mentor: Tobias Thierer (Biomatters Ltd.)

Abstract: The aim is to implement existing algorithms that utilise phylogenetic information to prioritize species for biodiversity conservation, and provide a GUI to these algorithms.

APPENDIX VI.2 – STUDENT EVALUATIONS FOR JOE FAIL’S COURSE

Teaching an Elementary Story of Life

Participant Evaluation Comments

- 1: This workshop was incredible! The instructor, Joe Fail, brought such passion to the subject area...he motivated all of us! The content, the "story", tied together the different science topics in a way I thought would be impossible. I have a much better understanding of the principles of Science after completing this workshop. It will enable me to teach Science to my students in a way I never thought possible...I believe I will easily be able to instill the love of Science in my students! A++ Joe Fail! The content was amazing...almost as amazing as our instructor! I hope there will be more workshops of this magnitude in the future. It is exactly what elementary science needs!
- 2: This workshop was exciting and useful. We learned very interesting things that were helpful in expanding my own background knowledge of science. I now feel more competent to teach these concepts to students, because of a better understanding that I have. The workshop gave me some great hands on activities that I definitely plan to use in my room.
- 3: I was unsure of what to expect of this workshop before attending, due to the information sent beforehand. It seemed very difficult for myself, not only my third graders. After the fact I am so glad I had the opportunity to attend this session! Joe is an excellent teacher and I learned so much useful information to carry back to my students. I am even thankful for the knowledge that I have gained about this subject matter for my own every day life. I do not feel this would have been as well taught by any other teacher. Joe's passion and dedication for this showed throughout the week!!!
- 4: This was a very challenging experience, but one that I will remember often as I plan my science lessons in the future. It helped me as a learner, and I find myself even now reflecting on all that we experienced during this week.
- 5: I thoroughly enjoyed this workshop and I thought NCSSM did a great job hosting it. I'd love to attend another workshop there; I hope you have some elementary science opportunities in the future.
- 6: It was a lot of material to cover in a week, but Joe did a great job tying things together and making it meaningful. He was very responsive to students' needs and suggestions. I think other teachers could also benefit. Thank you.
- 7: Outstanding workshop. I recommend this to all elementary education science teachers.
- 8: I was skeptical at first, but I believe this will work out. I am willing to give it a try. Joe was very knowledgeable.
- 9: Learned a great deal. Outstanding instructor. Very thorough.
- 10: My "D" above in #11 is about appropriate time, in reference to the length of the days we were in the workshop. The material was very interesting and challenging, the labs were fun and relevant, and there were some lively and enlightening discussions during the class time. There wasn't time wasted at all-- but it is a very long day when you're sitting from 8:30 until 5:00ish. We as teachers aren't used to sitting at all during the course of our regular day! After lunch was especially difficult, because we often had to take turns keeping one another awake! This is no insult to Joe, because the massive info was presented

in a logical story fashion and was not boring, BUT sitting still after lunch in a small room was so difficult for most of us. I wish I had the magic solution, but because of the magnitude of information presented, I know it has to be long hours--maybe one of those classroom days (Tues.?) could be split into two parts--maybe 8:30 - 1:00, and then 4 til 7?? I don't know how that would go, but I saw a lot of sleepy eyes after lunch, and I hate to admit mine weren't exempt!! Thank you for the opportunity to participate in the workshop--we were well taken care of, and were presented with relevant information!

- 11:** Jo was very passionate about this workshop. He did everything in his power to help me "get" the curriculum. This passion rubbed off. Even though I felt like much of the information was above my elementary years, I am a more educated person and will be a more worthwhile science teacher after attending this workshop. Joe's strengths were the avid conversation and questioning techniques. His knowledge about this subject was phenomenal. The workshop's weaknesses were labs and lack of movement for which an elementary educator is accustomed. However, the strengths, and profound information learned, outweighed any weakness that could be due in part to lack of my own personal background or knowledge about the subject. I would love to attend future workshops, lectures, or field work with Jo.

Appendix VII.1.				
NESCent Student Interns				
2006 - 2008				
Last Name	First Name	Project	Mentor	
Undergraduate Student Interns				
<i>Duke University</i>				
	Blohm	Cynthia	Development of evolution curriculum for elementary students	Fail
	Bullock	Allison	Ecological and morphological diversification of characiform fishes	Sidlauskas
	Gonsahn	Meredith	Evolution, ecology and earth history	Kidd/Price
	Haigler	Laura	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting	Sturkey
	Hamilton	Amy	What factors determine the distribution of parasites among cetaceans?	Price
	Hardie	Frances	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Collecting data on parenchyma and fiber distribution in xylem sapwood	Zanne
	Jackson-Ricketts*	Justine	The relationship between swimming speeds, diving capabilities and dietary strategies in whales and dolphins	Price
	Lavantucksin	Michael	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Collection of plant phylogenies for large families the wood density and vessel anatomy databases to increase intra family relationships	Kidd/Price
	Lotker	Michelle	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Data collection on maximum plant heights	Zanne
	Mitra	Oindri	Computational retrieval and printing systems for NESCent's call for proposals	Auman
	Saucier	Laura	The role of phylogeny and allometry in determining cetacean life history strategies	Price
	Schmidt	Jacob	Database on fossil cetaceans, to record age, taxonomy and most importantly size	Price
	Wong	Jessica	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Data collection on maximum plant heights	Zanne
<i>North Carolina State University</i>				
	Bosnjak	Diane	Website development/maintenance, database research	EOG
	Helder	Kelly	Science journalism intern program: Interviews with NESCent scientists	EOG
<i>University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill</i>				
	Thomson	Claire	Investigation of issues related to the use of ontology terms in phenotypic descriptions using NESCent-developed software	Cronk/Balhoff

NESCent Student Interns			
2006 - 2008			
Last Name	First Name	Project	Mentor
Graduate Student Interns			
<i>Duke University</i>			
Debroy	Nihshanka	Development and implementation of statistical models to test the effects of geography on species diversification	Ganapathy
<i>North Carolina State University</i>			
Yongsteadt	Elsa	Science journalism intern program: Evolution in the news	EOG
<i>University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill</i>			
Carrier	Sarah	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository	Greenberg
Diamond	Sarah	Development of NESCent science and synthesis products relating to awards	Kingsolver
Dube	Jackson	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository	Greenberg
Monnig	Ruth	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository	Greenberg
Ragland	Greg	Development of NESCent science and synthesis products relating to awards	Kingsolver
Thompson	Abbey	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository	Greenberg
White	Holly	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository	Greenberg
Interns Who Recently Completed Bachelors Degree			
<i>Duke University</i>			
Hu	Felix	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Data collection on maximum plant heights and parenchyma and fiber distribution in xylem sapwood	Zanne
McDowell	Ruth	Logistical support for NESCent working groups and catalysis group	Sturkey
Intern Who Recently Completed Ph.D.			
<i>Duke University</i>			
Ray	Rupa	Development of evolution curriculum for elementary students	Fail
*Through encouragement from her Mentor, Justine Jackson-Ricketts applied for and received an internship for summer 2007 doing field research on dolphins in Florida.			
African American students shown in bold.			

Appendix VII.2.

Student Interns

Report of the Senior Advisory Board for the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (NESCent), August 2007

Overview

The SAB visited NESCent on 23 and 24 August, 2007. We met with faculty, leaders, staff, and postdoctoral scholars, as well as with Duke University's Vice Provost for Research, James Siedow. We were joined for most discussions by officials from the National Science Foundation. We had been provided with copies of the annual report and the report from the site visit, which took place last January.

We were impressed with the rapid progress and overall success of NESCent in the past year. The progress in addressing problem areas identified in earlier SAB visits and in the site visit has been remarkable. Director Kathleen Smith and Associate Director Todd Vision have done outstanding jobs at addressing previously perceived weaknesses at NESCent, and all of the NESCent participants have been successful in building on the existing strengths of the center. Associate Director Joel Kingsolver continues to oversee an active and broad science program that has brought to NESCent a large cross-section of evolutionary biologists from across the country in many different capacities (>500 in year 2, and >800 in year 3). The concerns of the site visit team about the breadth of coverage of NESCent activities has clearly been addressed (this appears to have been largely an effect of a small sample size at the time of the site visit). NESCent is rapidly growing to meet the vision of a national center that coordinates, encourages, and promotes the development of evolutionary biology research, education, training, and synthesis.

Given that the SAB is impressed with the successes of NESCent, we have decided to focus our report on areas where additional improvement can and should occur. We also comment on some recommendations in the second-year site visit report. Many of our recommendations are meant to promote and encourage local discussion about the best ways to meet the current and future goals of the center. We believe the issues in this report are designed to help NESCent to put itself in the best position for a successful renewal by the National Science Foundation.

Directorship of NESCent

Dr. Kathleen Smith has done an extraordinary job of shepherding NESCent through its somewhat tumultuous beginnings. Her intelligent, calm, and consultative style has fostered an environment where NESCent is now realizing its potential. Although Dr. Smith has indicated that she would like to step down as director, she has generously agreed to continue her half-time directorship through the submission of NESCent's renewal. It would be very difficult to attract a new director to NESCent at this time if his or her first task was to prepare for a site visit and renewal in 2008.

The SAB feels that the directorship of NESCent should become a full-time position and that a new director should be recruited nationally. As NESCent continues to grow and

fulfill its mission, the duties of the director have increased. Accordingly, only a full-time director can manage the administration of NESCent. We note that NCEAS has a full-time director.

In addition, we recommend that the new director should be reviewed biennially. Such reviews could be part of the SAB meeting and need not be lengthy. But, a mechanism for formal review should be in place to address any issues or problems that might arise in the future.

Sabbatical Scholars

As noted in the recent review of NESCent, the presence of senior scientists at the Center is important to its intellectual tenor, and to the mentoring of the Postdoctoral Scholars. However, although Sabbatical Scholars are important, it has been difficult to attract top scholars on a regular basis. Some of this is related to NESCent being early in its reign, but experience at the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis suggests that this situation may persist even after NESCent matures.

The Center's leadership has recognized this and has initiated efforts to promote special opportunities to attract Sabbatical Scholars. Accordingly, we encourage the Center to continue to advertise these opportunities, which include full and short-term sabbaticals (perhaps during summers when scientists are less encumbered with other university responsibilities). Note that interested parties may include scholars in disciplines not typically characterized as evolutionary biologists (e.g., sociologists, economists, medical professionals, as well as those interested in education and outreach, and informatics). We suggest that the Center consider some embellishments of this programs to include very short stays – weeks – and opportunities for 2-3 researchers to spend similar periods together at the Center to collaborate.

Although all of the activities at NESCent will naturally benefit from proactive recruitment, the sabbatical program might be most improved by such efforts. The solicitation could come in at least two forms, the traditional one being through the scientific staff and associates of the Center, who should be attentive to scientists and topics that would most benefit from the NESCent opportunities. One interesting possibility is to have the Postdoctoral Scholars identify and invite appropriate sabbatical visitors. The resultant interactions with senior scientists will benefit the Postdoctoral Scholars, and an invitation from them might hold special appeal to sabbatical visitors, perhaps particularly for short visits. Another possibility is to recruit emeritus faculty, many of whom will have valuable data sets that need archiving and synthesis; and emeritus visitors may also be an important resource for Postdoctoral Scholars.

Although many scholars take sabbaticals to focus on their research, often by reducing their other responsibilities, prospective Sabbatical Scholars should be told explicitly that they are expected to initiate interactions with the postdoctoral scientists, and to be open to interactions if sought by these young scholars.

Postdoctoral Scholars

The postdoctoral program is designed to enable young scholars to develop synthetic skills and interests, beyond what would be expected in a traditional postdoctoral position. Moreover, postdocs design and run their own program, rather than step into (or sometimes complement) an existing project in someone's laboratory. In this regard, NESCent postdocs are similar to Michigan or Miller Fellows. This independence is both an opportunity and a challenge, and it requires that postdocs be self-directed, self-motivated, and able to seek out advice when needed.

The Board was impressed with the overall quality, breadth, and productivity of the postdoctoral program; and we enthusiastically recommend that it should remain an integral program of the mission. We do have some suggestions that are geared largely to the special challenges that NESCent postdocs face. We address as well some specific issues that we were asked to consider.

•*Quality and diversity.*—NESCent intends to support approximately 15 total postdocs per year. Currently 12 postdocs are in residence, and the Center receives about 25 – 35 applications per year. The selection committee evaluates the importance and innovation of the proposed project, whether it is synthetic (in the sense of pulling together existing data, analytical tools, and/or theory), as well as the promise and independence of the applicants themselves. Trying to achieve broad programmatic coverage has been a secondary issue thus far, primarily because the applicant pool has been exceptionally broad. In our view the selection criteria and their implementation have been effective, as the postdocs and their projects and presentations were of high quality and diverse.

•*Mentorship of postdocs.*—Each postdoc has a faculty mentor, and both get together on a regular basis. Postdocs submit a progress report each year, and these are evaluated and discussed by NESCent faculty. Of course, some postdocs will need little or no mentoring, but others might need advice, given the high degree of independence required to thrive in this type of postdoc. Nonetheless, in some cases opportunities for postdocs to interact with mentors and other senior scientists in general need to be increased. In part, this can be addressed by attracting more senior scientists, as discussed above.

•*Is synthesis a component of postdoctoral projects?*—A basic goal of NESCent is to foster synthetic research, and so we tried to evaluate not only the synthetic nature of projects, but also whether working at NESCent had altered research trajectories of the postdocs. Time constraints made this difficult to judge, but the Board's overall impression is that most projects are synthetic and innovative – some remarkably so. Thus the NESCent postdoctoral experience seemed to be working as envisioned.

Ultimately, having postdocs regularly involved with other activities in the Center (e.g., catalysis and working groups) may have a long-term impact on their careers, simply because Center postdocs may imprint on synthesis as a viable and exciting way of speeding their own scientific progress. Whether this in fact occurs will take time to assess, but one sign would be if former postdocs continue to be involved with NESCent.

•*Are postdocs cross-linking with other NESCent activities?*—One way for postdocs to link with other Center activities is to participate in catalysis meetings and working groups. This happens on some occasions, but apparently some group organizers have opposed this. The Board recommends that organizers of these activities should be strongly encouraged to welcome postdocs in their activities, and their willingness to do so might be factored into the selection process.

Postdocs are directly involved in outreach. Importantly, they give seminars at nearby colleagues, some of which are HMUs; and we hope this program will continue, as it benefits both the visited institutions and the postdocs themselves.

Postdocs do take advantage of seminars and reading groups at Duke and to some extent at UNC and NC State. This requires an effort on their part, but they should strongly be encouraged to continue making those efforts on a regular basis.

•*Interactions within NESCent?*—NESCent provides a venue to catalyze postdoc with postdoc interactions, and postdoc with sabbatarian interactions. Postdocs have a reading group, which encourages exchange. These groups have been self-directed, but we endorse the current plan to have one staff scientist participate in each reading group. The postdocs expressed appreciation for some visiting scientists, who were very interactive. Postdocs might encourage such interactions by meeting with new sabbatarians and seeing if they could organize a reading group of mutual interest. That would be exciting for both groups.

•*Career development.*—The staff is providing advice on career development (e.g., preparing a strong c.v. and statements of teaching and research). This program should be continued, as career mentorship is often neglected in graduate and postdoctoral training.

•*Job-placement success.*—One metric of the effectiveness of a program is its record of placing postdocs in good jobs. The numbers are of course still small, but NESCent postdocs have been quite successful so far. Two have taken postdocs elsewhere (U. Maryland, Duke), two others have taken faculty positions (U. Mississippi, U. Oregon), and one will take a position at U. Missouri, St. Louis.

•*Two versus three years.*—Initially postdoctoral appointments were to be for two years, but extension to a third year has become an option. We support this extension, but only on a case-by-case basis. Some synthetic projects take time to develop and mature, and so providing a third year of support to productive postdocs can be beneficial. This comes at a cost, of course, in that fewer postdocs will experience the NESCent community. So we feel a third year should only be offered when the benefit is substantial. Center faculty are well aware of the trade-offs, and have been careful in deciding whether to offer a third year of support.

•*Size of the program.*—Fifteen postdocs is substantially smaller than the number of postdocs at NCEAS. This raises the question of whether the size of NESCent

postdoctoral group is below the critical mass in a field as diverse as evolution. Expanding the size right now is not an immediate option, but we encourage NESCent to consider the feasibility and utility of requesting (in the renewal) a slightly larger group of postdocs. This might come at a cost in the number of sabbatical visitors, so the decision will not be easy.

•*Recommendations.*—Overall, we were impressed with the postdoctoral program. We encourage postdocs and faculty at NESCent to get together regularly and to discuss ways to identify any general concerns, to evaluate how to rectify those concerns as well as to enhance the program. Prior to preparing the renewal proposal, all concerned should also try to evaluate whether the size of the postdoctoral group is adequate. Input from former postdocs should be sought, as their insights might prove very informative.

Informatics Program

Informatics at NESCent is in a very strong position, in large part to the efforts of Dr. Todd Vision, Associate Director for Informatics. Dr. Vision is clearly an exceptional asset to the Center. Under his leadership informatics has become a core part of activities at NESCent, and he has obtained substantial grant funding for informatics projects from both the NIH and NSF. Currently, his position involves a 25% time commitment from UNC, but we strongly endorse the recommendation of the site visit team that a 50% time commitment from UNC for this position is more appropriate and necessary for the healthy functioning of the informatics program.

Basic IT support for NESCent activities has vastly improved compared the situation encountered by the site visit. Tools for supporting working groups and catalysis meetings are well developed, and include easy access for participants to the wireless network, and collaborative wikis created for each catalysis or workgroup meeting prior to the start of that meeting.

The Dryad digital archive project has the potential to be a very important resource for the evolutionary biology community — this is reflected in the success NESCent has had in obtaining expressions of support from major scientific societies and journals in the field of evolutionary biology. This is a timely project that individual societies and publishers have either been unwilling or unable to undertake. In addition to the obvious advantages of archiving hard-won data, it would create a valuable source of data for synthetic meta-analyses in the future.

The Informatics training programs have been successful, involving both a formally taught course, and overseeing eleven Google Summer of Code students. The Summer of Code project resulted in significant amounts of open source code being deposited in the Google Code repository. The momentum established by these courses, and by the "hackathons" should be maintained, and would serve to cement NESCent's reputation for facilitating interaction between developers of tools for evolutionary biology. The Informatics

Advisory Group suggested developing training activities for synthetic tools, such as datamining material stored in Dryad and other databases to generate data for meta-analyses.

Informatics has an Informatics Advisory Group (IAG) with seven members. Although the IAG has served a valuable role in providing feedback to the Informatics staff, we suggest that the Informatics group is now sufficiently well established that the role of the IAG be changed to that of being a pool of advisors that the ADI can call upon for advice as needed. Now that the Senior Advisory Board has several members with an informatics background, it makes sense for the SAB to take over the role of reviewing the informatics program.

Institutional Support

The Center was originally proposed as a combined effort of the three universities of the Research Triangle. As the Center has developed, however, institutional support has become somewhat lopsided, with by far the largest financial commitment coming from Duke. The reasons for this are largely historical, but it is clear to the SAB that now is an appropriate time for all three institutions to review the considerable success of NESCent, the contributions it is making and can continue to make to all three universities, and what would be a reasonable level of support from each. Our major recommendation on this subject, therefore, is that Jim Siedow (Vice Provost for Research at Duke) join with his counterparts at NCSU and UNC and meet at NESCent with the Director and Associate Directors to consider future relationships among the Center and the Universities and future funding commitments. This should take place as soon as possible, so that revised levels of institutional support can be evaluated as part of the site visit early next year.

All three universities have strong connections to the Center. At present, Duke is represented at the Center by Kathleen Smith (Director); in addition, all post-docs are affiliated with departments at Duke. UNC is represented by Joel Kingsolver (Associate Director for Science) and Todd Vision (Associate Director for Informatics). NCSU is represented at the center by current Associate Director Greg Gibson and future AD Brian Wiegmann. All are central to the operation of the Center and are in large part responsible for the overall success of the Center. In addition, NESCent collaborates with Library Sciences at UNC, and the Digital Library program at NCSU is a partner in the Dryad project.

At present, Duke University contributes more than \$300,000 per annum to NESCent. This money covers rent for the space in which the Center is housed, a budget for the Director for expenses not usually covered by NSF, and lab support that permits Director Kathleen Smith to maintain her research program. This is in addition to the salary support of Dr. Smith. Neither UNC nor NCSU appear to provide any direct financial support to the Center.

The SAB sees a clear argument for an increased financial commitment from UNC. An obvious form for this support would be to assist Todd Vision, in light of his current contributions to the Center, and the ongoing importance of his expertise. The NESCent grant currently pays a part of Dr. Vision's salary. He has been quite successful at generating external funding, and now holds several grants that are administered through UNC for support of work at NESCent. Additional substantial grants have been submitted. We strongly encourage UNC to consider increasing Dr. Vision's release time from teaching from 25% to 50%, so that he can spend half time at NESCent. In addition, funds for a post-doc or research associate (perhaps \$50,000 per year) would help him to maintain his own research program in the face of his heavy commitment to NESCent.

Currently \$200,000 per year from the NESCent grant is flowing through NCSU to support education and outreach. However, there seems to be no reciprocal financial commitment from NCSU to NESCent. The SAB sees two possibilities: either 1) the money currently administered by NCSU should be shifted to flow through Duke, or 2) NCSU should make more of a direct contribution to NESCent. Although the SAB sees considerable advantages arising from option 2 for both NCSU and NESCent, any decision should be a part of the joint discussion among the three host institutions.

Education and Outreach

The education and outreach group (EOG) of NESCENT has noticeably increased its organization and focus since the last SAB meeting. The board recognizes and compliments the hard work and commitment evident from Kristen Jenkins and Jory Weintraub, the two primary EOG staff members.

A primary focus for the upcoming year should be to integrate education and outreach across the activities of the center. The current Associate Director (Greg Gibson) is departing, having taken a new faculty position in Australia. This transition to a new Associate Director makes this the appropriate time for a self-assessment of the organizational structure of the EOG, as well as the focus of the EOG activities. The clearly stated importance of education and outreach in NESCent's renewal process, conveyed by the EF program director present at the SAB meeting, is an important reason to make this assessment a priority.

•*Organization of EOG.*—The Center has proposed to have Brian Wiegmann (NC State) replace Greg Gibson. Given Dr. Wiegmann's current level of participation at the Center, enthusiasm for the Center's mission, and expertise in evolutionary studies, we feel he will make a valuable addition to the NESCent directors. However, the EOG would also benefit from support from a faculty member specifically trained in education and outreach. In particular, someone already vested in outreach to the local minority serving institutions would be beneficial. This individual could become a member of NESCent's Operations Board and serve to advise the EOG on a regular basis. The SAB also recommends that if Dr. Wiegmann is to assume an advisory role to the EOG, he provide a short supplemental report of what he considers EOG is currently doing right and what directions he feels the EOG should prioritize.

It might be worthwhile at this time consider moving away from the current structure where each of the triangle universities is linked to a particular responsibility (e.g., NC State's current linkage to Education and Outreach). Each university should contribute faculty and other resources according to its own strengths.

The site visit team pointed out an indication of a lack of intensity between the former Associate Director and the EOG staff. This would be important to remedy as quickly as possible. One possible solution (of which there are many) is to start a regular meeting between the EOG staff and representatives of the other groups in the center, to facilitate integration of outreach across the activities of the center.

•*Present focus of activities.*—EOG formed two working groups (Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU) and Evolution Education) to strategize effective outreach activities and developed a targeted sabbatical focused on development of education outreach projects. The working group and sabbaticals have produced products (databases, a 4th grade curriculum, a travel grants program) that demonstrate unique contributions of NESCent to science outreach. The Board recommends continuing this approach, with the added advice of including mechanisms to assess effective outcomes. The EOG has implemented an Evolution Symposia series at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual meeting and generates a CD-ROM and web broadcast on each year's topic. Its impact, as currently assessed by immediate feedback to the organizers at the symposia, was strong and universally positive. The board agrees this is a great idea and strongly supports a model of 'teach the teachers'. We recommend continuing facilitation of the annual symposia and including in the design a method for assessing the success and degree of impact of the symposia on teachers in attendance. Even simple data, like number of teachers present, grade levels, states, and minority serving institutions represented would be beneficial for the upcoming site visit/renewal. Similarly, continued participation at SACNAS and North Carolina State Teachers Association meeting seem appropriate avenues for NESCent to impact evolution education.

The EOG posts regular podcasts that distill recent findings in evolutionary biology on their website. Under a similar umbrella are activities that encompass other science journalism activities. These activities provide a valuable training opportunity for NESCent scientists and undergraduates from the local universities in communicating science simply and clearly to the public (and makes the website look cool!). Other activities include publicizing NESCent science, development and maintenance of a website with an increasing number of resources for the community, facilitating postdoc professional development, and development of a broader impact resource center/database. All of these are excellent examples of integration of education/outreach across the center activities. These activities are critical to the function of the center and are being carried with excellence.

•Recommendations for the future:

- The priority should be to decompartmentalize the education/outreach activities. Integration of education and outreach should be operating with much cross-talk between the groups at NESCent. To some degree this is a matter of how education/outreach activities are presented to review boards. Broadening participation in education/outreach at all levels of the NESCent's activities was advised by the NSF officers present.
- Given the agreed significance of teaching teachers, including those at minority serving institutions, attendance at other state level teacher association meetings might be valuable. National Center for Science Education could be one resource for information on regional meetings that would most greatly benefit from the types of resources NESCent can provide.
- Utilize the synthetic computational expertise at the center to make a unique contribution to education and outreach. Examples noted above are potentially significant contributions on this front. Additional brain-storming could help foster the creation of NESCent unique contributions to evolutionary outreach.
- Encourage assessment. The SAB recognizes the difficulty of doing quality assessment of Center activities. Nonetheless, it is worthwhile pursuing in some fashion. This process could be facilitated by above noted addition of an individual trained in education research to the operations board. The renewal proposal might also include budgeted funds for carrying out quality assessment.
- Rather than extending and increasing the number and kind of activities the EOG participates in, we encourage leveraging limited resources by collaborating/connecting/facilitating with existing groups or individuals working toward similar ends.
- Both Jory Weintraub and Kirsten Jenkins are clearly motivated and becoming experts in various aspects of education outreach. We encourage increasing their leadership roles and responsibilities, ensuring they have adequate opportunity to continue their training and encouraging a climate of respect for their activities in the Center.

Major Initiatives

The SAB agreed that NESCent should be proactive in initiating activities promoting synthesis in evolutionary biology. The SAB recognized the risk of spreading the Center's efforts too thin, but felt that several of the initiative ideas discussed during our visit have strong potential for significant impact with a relatively modest investment of resources. Three especially promising ones are listed here without prioritization.

1. "Evolution 2020" – a series of short synthetic essays (~1500 words) on where the field should be in another decade. This series could promote innovative research both within and beyond evolutionary biology, particularly if its aims to produce papers that are aspirational rather than predictive. The suggested design is very promising, with NESCent bringing in one or two outside people to spend a few days at the Center brainstorming with one another and with NESCent postdocs and other participants; this will have the added benefits of increasing the number of senior scientists interacting with the postdocs and further publicizing Center activities. Several kinds of papers could be

targeted, including (a) pairing an evolutionary biologist with someone from an area that is less evolutionary in outlook (e.g. cell biology); (b) pairing workers across temporal or spatial scales (e.g. population genetics and evolutionary paleobiology); (c) stimulating perspectives/outlooks on longstanding “great debate” topics (e.g. group selection, neutral vs. adaptive change). The series could be posted on the NESCent website and published in a journal whose papers are indexed by search engines such as the Web of Science.

2. A combination of “Genomics 2020” and “Disseminating the Tree of Life,” exploring the areas where the two overlap. Integrating these evolutionary genomics efforts, and making their results available to broader communities in, and beyond, evolutionary biology would be extremely valuable. This might readily mesh with the excellent EOG project led by Sam Donovan aimed at bringing tree-based thinking into undergraduate education. One element of this initiative might be to host one of NCBI’s workshops on using NCBI’s tools and resources (which are funded by NCBI), but with the aim of this being a two-way exchange. Appropriate NCBI personnel could be invited to interact with NESCent and other area participants to explore ways to improve the utility of NCBI tools to the evolutionary community. At the same time, the workshop would attract many area biologists to NESCent, and would help NCBI meet its outreach goals, so it would be a win-win situation for both NESCent and NCBI.

3. “Evolution and global change.” Although this broad topic is being addressed by many scientific communities, from evolutionary genetics to conservation biology to Quaternary (and older) paleoecology, these communities rarely talk to one another. Synthesis across systems and perspectives would thus be extremely valuable (indeed the need for synthesis in this area was emphasized by a 2005 NRC report), and would be an excellent vehicle for coordination with NCEAS. A large number of promising cross-disciplinary issues arose in discussions of this topic: whether biotic features that promote invasiveness also promote mobility in the face of global change, the reconciliation of coevolved sets of species with the apparently individualistic behavior of species during Quaternary climate oscillations, and the relation between extinction selectivity and intensity during times of global change; these, and many others, present opportunities for synthesis that will be of interest to both basic and applied evolutionary research.

[The NRC report referred to above is “The Geological Record of Ecological Dynamics: Understanding the Biotic Effects of Future Environmental Change”
<http://www.nap.edu/catalog/11209.html>]

Senior Advisory Board, August 2007 meeting

David Hillis, Chair, University of Texas-Austin

Ray Huey, University of Washington

David Jablonski, University of Chicago

Elizabeth Kellogg, University of Missouri-St. Louis

Lisa Nagy, University of Arizona

Rod Page, University of Glasgow

O. J. Reichman, National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis

Barbara Schaal, Washington University in St. Louis

Not attending 2007 meeting (but approved report):

Judy Diamond, University of Nebraska State Museum

Scott Edwards, Harvard University

Jonathan Pritchard, University of Chicago

Simon Tavaré, University of Southern California

NESCent Organizational Chart September, 2007

